

BEHAVIORAL RECOGNITION TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract

The rapid adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) by regulatory agencies marks a fundamental shift in legal compliance and enforcement. While law and policy debates have heatedly focused on the threat of AI biometric tools such as facial recognition technology (FRT) to privacy and equality, the field of AI-driven *behavioral recognition technology* (BRT) has been far less charted. In contrast to FRT, BRT uses machine learning not simply to identify *who* a person is but to predict *what* they are likely to do. Agencies from the IRS to the EPA increasingly deploy these algorithmic tools to predict individual and corporate behavior and the likelihood of regulatory violations, yet legal scholarship has focused more narrowly on government use of AI in policing and criminal law enforcement. This Article demonstrates that as governments and administrative agencies embrace BRT to make fine-grained determinations about whom to trust and whom to monitor, investigate, audit, or sanction—and in turn to determine how to allocate limited enforcement resources—behavioral prediction becomes a central technology of governance.

In providing the first comprehensive legal framework for evaluating and ethically implementing BRT, this Article makes three key contributions. First, it maps how regulatory agencies are using AI-driven technology to make nuanced determinations about whom to trust and monitor, revealing an emerging regulatory paradigm that accelerates a paradigm shift from traditional command-and-control approaches toward data-driven trust assessments. Second, it argues that while deploying BRT as a regulatory practice raises significant constitutional and

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administrative law concerns regarding privacy, equality, and autonomy, properly designed systems can enhance these values by enabling more individualized and evidence-based enforcement decisions, as opposed to random selection or demographic-based proxies. Third, it develops a novel normative blueprint for responsible deployment of BRT in regulatory enforcement. The Article establishes a set of principles including the privileging of individual over group-based predictions, requiring strong empirical justification for public sector cross-domain data use, and dynamic balancing of predictive accuracy with civil rights protection. Rather than embracing or rejecting BRT wholesale, as has too often been the case with debates and policies on FRT, we chart a dynamic path forward that harnesses these tools' benefits while preserving democratic values and individual rights. The Article concludes by offering practical guidance for courts and agencies evaluating and implementing these emerging technologies.

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INTRODUCTION

AI is set to revolutionize not only private markets but also the legal process of regulation, enforcement, and compliance. Contemporary technological advancements with corresponding policy developments underscore both the promises and risks of this moment. Behavioral recognition technology (BRT) systems are rapidly pervading the work of government agencies, leveraging machine learning and big data to identify, classify, and predict human and organizational behavior based on patterns of actions over time. Agencies are increasingly relying on such AI tools to make dynamic trust determinations that structure how they allocate scarce enforcement resources. Instead of basing decisions on static criteria, random audits, or categorical suspicion, modern enforcement systems now analyze *behavioral signatures*—patterns of conduct that emerge over time and that empirically correlate with compliance or violation risk.

The IRS’s fraud-detection models, the EPA’s operational-behavior anomaly systems, OSHA’s predictive workplace-safety algorithms, and the SEC’s market-manipulation surveillance tools all exemplify this shift: each agency now uses machine-learning models to detect behavior patterns such as filing sequences, operational deviations, reporting rhythms, safety-practice irregularities, or trading-pattern microstructures. The behavior patterns function as predictive proxies for regulated entities’ trustworthiness. These algorithmic systems assign individualized “trust scores” that determine who receives expedited processing, cooperative treatment, or reduced oversight, and who is instead flagged for inspection, audit, or investigation. As a result, behavioral recognition has begun to replace traditional command-and-control enforcement with a data-driven, probabilistic, and ostensibly more personalized model of regulatory trust.

While these technological developments are enabling shifts in regulatory oversight, they are also increasingly necessary in the face of a sweeping reduction in enforcement resources. In just the past few years, the federal government has experienced the cutting or freezing of over \$163 billion from programs across education, health, housing, and public safety, as well as the elimination of major grants and entire agencies in the name of deregulatory efficiency and cost

saving. Resources have been dramatically reduced through hiring freezes and large-scale layoffs, with the government announcing, in some instances, that it will seek to replace the cut employees with AI.¹

These new realities, culminating in the passage of what is known as the “One Big Beautiful Bill” in July 2025, are expected to accelerate the adoption of automated governance technologies and underscore the critical need for smart and ethical use of digital technology and data in the work of government.² Regulatory agencies face the ongoing challenge of ensuring compliance in an ever more complex world while seeing a decline in their enforcement resources. New regulatory methods are rapidly emerging, from predictive policing and credit scoring to algorithmic decision-making in inspection and enforcement. But though these developments are already underway, they are adopted unsystematically and are both undertheorized and lacking a robust analysis of their normative implications and practical impacts.

Over the past decade, facial recognition technology (FRT) and other biometric technologies have been a focal point in the legal and policy debates about AI regulation, prompting extensive litigation, legislative proposals, and civil-rights advocacy.³ Because facial recognition directly implicates such concerns as identity and anonymity rights, surveillance, and differential error rates across demographic groups, it became the paradigmatic example of “high-risk AI” and the subject of reforms ranging from municipal bans and moratoria to comprehensive state and federal regulatory proposals.⁴ FRT invoked a number of constitutional questions: whether

¹ Ashley Wu et al., *Where Trump, Musk and DOGE Have Cut Federal Workers So Far*, N.Y. TIMES (Mar. 12, 2025), <https://www.nytimes.com/interactive/2025/02/11/us/politics/trump-musk-doge-federal-workers.html>; Jason Wingard, *Musk Replacing Workers with AI: Should You Be Worried?*, FORBES (Mar. 10, 2025), <https://www.forbes.com/sites/jasonwingard/2025/03/10/musk-replacing-workers-with-ai-should-you-be-worried/>; Exec. Order 14222 of Feb. 26, 2025: Implementing the President’s “Department of Government Efficiency” Cost Efficiency Initiative, 90 Fed. Reg. 11095 (Mar. 3, 2025), <https://www.federalregister.gov/d/2025-03527>.

² See, e.g., Nicol Turner Lee, *How Federal Layoffs Set the Stage for Greater Privatization and Automation of the US Government*, BROOKINGS (Jan. 30, 2025), <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/how-federal-layoffs-set-the-stage-for-greater-privatization-and-automation-of-the-u-s-government/>; Douglas MacMillan et al., *The Government Wants AI to Fight Wars and Review Your Taxes*, THE WASHINGTON POST (July 15, 2025), <https://www.washingtonpost.com/business/2025/07/14/trump-ai-government-war-taxes-jobs/>.

³ See, e.g., THE CAMBRIDGE HANDBOOK OF FACIAL RECOGNITION IN THE MODERN STATE (R. Matulionyte & M. Zalnierute eds., 2024); Andrew Guthrie Ferguson, *Facial Recognition and the Fourth Amendment*, 105 MINN. L. REV. 1105 (2021); Joseph A. Tomain, *Facial Recognition Technology and the First Amendment*, 32 MICH. TECH. L. REV. (forthcoming 2026); Elizabeth E. Joh, *Facial Recognition Technology in Policing: An American Experiment*, 6 EUR. REV. DIGIT. ADMIN. & L. (2025); Nikhil Naren & Amresh Mishra, *Dissecting the Regulatory Landscape of Facial Recognition Technology*, in RETHINKING THE POLICE FOR A BETTER FUTURE (B.N. Mukherjee & Ors. eds. 2024); Matthew B. Kugler, *Public Perceptions can Guide Regulation of Public Facial Recognition*, 25 COLUMBIA SCI. & TECH. L. REV. 1 (2023); Gupta, Yash, *Facial Recognition Technology and Fundamental Right to Privacy* (April 10, 2025); Elizabeth A. Rowe, *Regulating Facial Recognition Technology in the Private Sector*, 24 STAN. TECH. L. REV. 1 (2020). A Google Scholar search of Facial Recognition Technology brings in over 17,800 results only since 2021.

⁴ See generally Rashida Richardson, *Facial Recognition in the Public Sector: The Policy Landscape*, GMF POLICY BRIEF (Feb. 2021), <https://www.gmfus.org/sites/default/files/Richardson%2520-%2520Facial%2520recognition.pdf>; Jameson Spivack & Clare Garvie, *A Taxonomy of Legislative Approaches to Face Recognition in the United States*,

pervasive automated identification constitutes a Fourth Amendment search,⁵ whether real-time public-space scanning chills First Amendment activity,⁶ and how equal protection and antidiscrimination principles apply when accuracy varies across races and genders.⁷ Some scholars have called FRT “the most dangerous surveillance tool ever invented” and argue that “given the unique threats this morally suspect tool poses to privacy, civil liberties, human flourishing, and democracy, the only appropriate response is a ban.”⁸

Meanwhile, against this backdrop, this article introduces the cluster of AI-driven technology, which it coins BRT, that has risen with relatively little attention, theorization, or policy reform. BRT expands the deployment of AI from biometric attributes and static characteristics to “behavioral signatures”— patterns and rhythms in conduct that can be associated with particular outcomes such as compliance propensities, fraud risk, safety practices, market manipulation, or the likelihood of future violations. Unlike biometric systems that recognize *who* someone is, BRT is more concerned with *how* an actor behaves: the timing of tax filings, the pattern of emissions reports, the cadence of safety logs, the structure of trading activity, or other repeatable conduct-based indicators. In regulatory settings, BRT is used to make trust predictions, enabling agencies to assign individualized risk or reliability profiles that guide monitoring, inspection, enforcement prioritization, or eligibility for self-certification programs. BRT systems analyze interaction patterns and digital traces and transform them into actionable regulatory inferences about trustworthiness, in turn potentially transforming regulatory enforcement into a system of continuous behavioral risk scoring. This Article illustrates that as governments and administrative agencies embrace BRT to make fine-grained determinations about whom to trust and whom to investigate, audit, or sanction, behavioral prediction becomes a central architecture of governance.

Integrating insights from behavioral economics and constitutional law, this Article analyzes the next phase of AI-driven regulatory enforcement. In contrast to traditional biometrics and rule-based targeting, BRT-based systems are designed to infer behavioral traits—such as honesty, cooperativeness, or compliance “culture”—and feed these predictions into resource allocation and penalty decisions across domains ranging from tax enforcement and environmental

in REGULATING BIOMETRICS: GLOBAL APPROACHES AND OPEN QUESTIONS 86, 89-94 (Amba Kak ed., Sep. 2020), <https://ainowinstitute.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/regulatingbiometrics-spivack-garvie.pdf>.

⁵ See, e.g., David C. Gray, *Bertillonage in an Age of Surveillance: Fourth Amendment Regulation of Facial Recognition Technologies*, 24 SMU SCI. & TECH. L. REV. 3 (2021).

⁶ See, e.g., Julian R. Murphy, *Chilling: The Constitutional Implications of Body-Worn Cameras and Facial Recognition Technology at Public Protests*, 75 WASH. & LEE L. REV. ONLINE 1 (2018); Apratim Vidyarthi, *The Public Square Has Eyes (or Cameras): Anonymous Speech under the First and Fourth Amendments in the Age of Facial Recognition*, 32 FORDHAM INTELL. PROP. MEDIA & ENT. L.J. 630 (2022).

⁷ See, e.g., Pawel Drozdowski et al., *Demographic Bias in Biometrics: A Survey on an Emerging Challenge*, 1 IEEE TRANSACTIONS IN TECH. & SOC. 89 (2020); Christopher Jones, *Law Enforcement Use of Facial Recognition: Bias, Disparate Impacts on People of Color, and the Need for Federal Legislation*, 22 N.C. J.L. & TECH. 777 (2021).

⁸ Woodrow Hartzog et al., *Normalizing Facial Recognition Technology and The End of Obscurity*, 6 EUR. REV. DIGIT. ADMIN. & L. 163 (2025).

compliance to workplace safety, consumer protection, and public benefits administration. This shift challenges the distinction between ex post detection of violations and ex ante prediction of who is deemed risky, making behavioral prediction itself a site of legal import and normative contestation.

This Article maps the emerging use of behavioral prediction in regulatory agencies' trust and monitoring strategies, revealing how BRT is used to decide who can be placed on "trusted trader" lists, who receives streamlined treatment, and who is subjected to heightened scrutiny or automated flags. The analysis reveals how algorithmic behavioral trust assessment raises constitutional and administrative law concerns, particularly around privacy, equality, and autonomy—systems that read and score choices and microbehaviors carry the risk of embedding stereotypes, policing demeanor, and punishing nonconformity, while also obscuring responsibility behind probabilistic models. This Article, however, argues that properly designed behavioral prediction systems can in principle vindicate these same values by enabling evidence-based enforcement that outperforms random audits, complaint-driven enforcement, or crude demographic proxies. This Article thereby proposes a normative blueprint for responsible deployment of BRT in regulatory enforcement. By centering on behavioral prediction as a regulatory technology, debates about government use of AI are reframed as questions about how far the state may go in modeling and acting upon citizens' bodies and behaviors. Rather than a binary choice between embracing or rejecting AI-powered enforcement wholesale, this Article charts a middle path that recognizes the inevitability of behavioral datafication while demanding new safeguards for rights. This path offers concrete guidance for courts, legislatures, and agencies on how to evaluate, authorize, and oversee BRT systems, while situating behavioral recognition within the longer history of state efforts to measure and manage human conduct.

This Article is the first to bridge contemporary trends in regulatory theory that focus on trust, enforcement escalation, and differentiation between good and bad actors, with the emergence of data-driven and AI-powered regulation. Building on the wealth of scholarship on effective public governance, this Article analyzes the role of predictive AI in propelling fundamental shifts in public processes, from traditional command-and-control models that rely heavily on punitive enforcement mechanisms to "new governance" approaches. These shifts introduce flexible, incentive-based compliance, escalate enforcement measures, and emphasize collaboration between regulators and regulated parties, flexibility in rulemaking, intrinsic motivations of regulated parties, and contextualization of regulations to individual situations.⁹

⁹ IAN AYRES & JOHN BRAITHWAITE, *RESPONSIVE REGULATION: TRANSCENDING THE DEREGULATION DEBATE* (1992); Orly Lobel, *The Renew Deal: The Fall of Regulations and the Rise of Governance in Contemporary Legal Thought*, 89 MINN. L. REV. 342 (2004); Jennifer Wang et al., *Distinguishing Predictive and Generative AI in Regulation*, UCLA SCH. OF L., Pub. L. Rsch. Paper No. 25-26 (2025).

While AI has been racing ahead in its development and adoption, law and legal scholarship about AI has evolved more narrowly, addressing AI's immediate risks to privacy and accountability. Moreover, the normative discussion on enforcement technologies has focused primarily on the use of AI in criminal justice and policing systems, where predictive regulation has evoked concerns that it enables or perpetuates discriminatory tropes (e.g., racially biased stop-and-frisk searches),¹⁰ is prone to inaccurate and unreliable assessments, and drives the gathering of data which may unduly invade privacy.¹¹ These accounts in legal scholarship have lacked a balanced approach that considers the costs and benefits of automation compared to human fallibility, resulting in large blind spots in the debate on AI's role in the regulatory process.¹² This Article, in contrast, recognizes both the risks and opportunities and argues there is a need for a robust and systematic ethical framework for the proliferating deployment of AI in the regulatory process. It accordingly presents an original normative framework grounded in three core principles.

First, regulation should adopt AI data-driven trust when it allows for more individualized predictions, moving away from group-based predictions. Algorithmic tools are often designed to exploit all available information to form usable distinctions between classes of people. Group-level trust is typically based on data points that attach predictors of compliance to social, cultural, ethnic, or other group affiliations. Regulatory agencies must leverage AI's newfound capabilities to reject group-based classification in favor of individualized trust.

Second, to support this shift to personalized predictions, agencies should consider algorithms' computational powers as an opportunity to move from blinding certain information to a new paradigm of fairness through awareness: a continuous check on the outcomes of the regulatory process. AI can help audit, learn, and improve regulation such that it increases fairness, transparency, and efficiency over time. The shift to AI-supported regulatory processes must entail a willingness to constantly track the government's own institutional history and correct regulatory inaccuracies and mistakes.

Third, norm violation in one regulatory context (e.g., traffic violation) should not be the basis of predictive enforcement in another regulatory context (e.g., tax evasion) unless the government has collected and presented sufficient data indicating that such inferences are empirically and substantially valid, and their use outweighs the social costs of monitoring trustworthiness across domains. Creating generalized individual "compliance scores" not tethered

¹⁰ Matthew Browning & Bruce Arrigo, *Stop and Risk: Policing, Data, and the Digital Age of Discrimination*, 46 AM. J. CRIM. JUST. 298 (2021). *But see* Nigar Hashimzade et al., *Predictive Analytics and the Targeting of Audits*, 124 J. ECON. BEHAV. & ORG. 130 (2016).

¹¹ Rainer Mühlhoff, *Predictive Privacy: Towards an Applied Ethics of Data Analytics*, 23 ETHICS & INFO. TECH. 675 (2021).

¹² Orly Lobel, *The AI Regulatory Pyramid: A Taxonomy & Analysis of the Emerging Toolbox in the Global Race for the Regulation and Governance of Artificial Intelligence*, 57 LOYOLA L. REV. 859 (2024).

to a single regulatory context should, as a default, be rejected. The idea of trust scoring has received much criticism and dystopic alarm—from Orwellian surveillance societies, through “Minority Report” scenarios of regulatory determinism, to the Chinese social credit system. Democratic societies should carefully consider exceptions based on well-founded evidence and normative deliberation. This Article shows how a constitutional balancing approach can guide government agencies and judicial oversight in implementing narrowly tailored exceptions.

Drawing on a wealth of interdisciplinary research, this Article emphasizes that trust-based regulation can enhance corporate cooperation and cohesion in ways less susceptible to harm than in the context of individual regulatory subjects. Unlike predictive policing or suspect identity-based social credit systems, focusing on corporate behavior and regulatory interactions may encourage voluntary participation while ensuring safeguards and ethical guardrails—including more accurate differentiation between trustworthy and non-trustworthy regulated entities, transparent criteria, learning and correction mechanisms, and rehabilitation mechanisms like reset provisions for rebuilding trust. For example, a chemical manufacturer with a strong environmental compliance record might receive expedited permit reviews, while a financial institution with consistently accurate filings could benefit from streamlined reporting requirements. In contrast to human regulatory subjects, such differential treatment of corporate actors carries significantly fewer stigmatizing effects that are captured by rights protections. It would therefore be more easily deployed and could also be used experimentally to study the efficacy of various BRTs.

This Article significantly advances pressing debates on implementing AI-powered trust-based regulatory systems by presenting a rich set of principles that will serve as design choices with profound contributions for any system seeking both administrative efficiency and constitutional rights protection. The back-and-forth on AI regulation between the Biden and Trump administrations’ executive orders reflects the need for such combined analysis. While President Biden’s order emphasized the risks involved in developing and using AI, President Trump’s order champions AI’s development as a means of national empowerment. Strikingly, neither administration has focused on guiding the government itself in using AI for regulatory enforcement and compliance. Seeking to fill this void, this Article provides a critical and systematic analysis of the perils and promises of AI-based regulation. It offers a roadmap for navigating these timely yet evergreen tensions between government efficiency and accountability.

By integrating contemporary insights from regulatory theory with the real-world implications of public sector AI adoption, this Article seeks to inform a more careful, democratic approach to AI regulatory governance. Regulators should not abandon the promise of AI to enhance trust and efficiency, but they must proceed with principled caution, institutional safeguards, and a clear-eyed understanding of the tradeoffs involved. The principles developed here—emphasizing individual over group predictions, limiting cross-domain data use, ensuring reversibility, and maintaining proportionality between effective AI use and continued civil rights

protection—will help regulators, courts, policymakers, and the public ensure that AI’s regulatory benefits are harnessed while preserving democratic values. This Article will also help guide future design and empirical study of new technologies’ deployment to assess their readiness and benefits.

The Article proceeds as follows. Part I presents the growing use of BRT in a broad range of regulatory fields—from food safety to financial compliance, tax administration to environmental regulation, child welfare to occupational safety—demonstrating the state’s accelerated interest in adopting BRT tools not only for criminal justice and policing but in all regulatory sectors. Part II introduces the implications of big data and AI for traditional regulatory practices, highlighting how these technologies are transforming an already changing landscape of regulation and governance. This section further shows how the accelerated shifts toward more flexible modes of regulation that rely on self-regulation and trust have created the perfect conditions for AI integration in the regulatory process. Part III presents the rich range of rights and interests that may be implicated with the introduction of AI-based BRT, including the rights to privacy, equality, and autonomy, as well as the potential social externalities of reduced solidarity and cohesion and amenability to strategic manipulation by sophisticated actors. Part IV develops a set of guidelines for policymakers and regulators, outlining how to integrate trust effectively while addressing the ethical and normative concerns inherent in the use of BRT. We develop a robust novel normative blueprint that will support the ethical design of trust-based regulatory technologies that rely on past behavior and cross-domain information, ensure accuracy and statistical sufficiency standards, and promote learning, transparency, and accountability. Part V presents the practical implications for the deployment of this blueprint to augment the current patchwork integration of AI into the work of government. This richer framework suggests a balanced and gradual implementation, starting first with corporations and later moving to personalized enforcement applied to individual regulated parties, allowing for experimentation, improvement, and democratic participation in the ongoing design of these systems. This Article concludes by delineating future research priorities and next steps. The frameworks developed in this Article call for a fundamental transformation of regulatory institutional design—requiring interdisciplinary expertise, novel accountability mechanisms, and robust empirical methodologies—to responsibly govern public sector algorithms whose complexity, opacity, and cross-domain reach exceed the capacities of traditional oversight models.

I. BRT IN REGULATION AND LAW ENFORCEMENT

A. *Predictive Enforcement: From Policing to Regulation*

In the criminal justice system, predictive tools have been used for decades. In the 1980s, the then-new sentencing guidelines aimed to provide more data-based, equitable means for

assessing individual sentences.¹³ The Correctional Offender Management Profiling for Alternative Sanctions (COMPAS), introduced in 1998, augmented this trend by introducing an algorithm that scores risks of recidivism.¹⁴ Beyond this use of algorithmic analysis in sentencing, automated means are involved in all stages of the law enforcement process today. Generally termed “predictive policing,” AI is increasingly deployed in police work to predict the likelihood of crime in given geographical locations, or at certain times, based on previous patterns of behavior.¹⁵ AI has also been used by law enforcement to determine whether particular individuals are likely to commit a crime or have already committed a crime.¹⁶

These algorithms are regularly deemed confidential and proprietary, such that the public has limited access to the factors and data used in making predictions.¹⁷ However, there is a general understanding that the factors used include an individual’s past history of offending; their age; whether criminal activity has been increasing or decreasing; geolocation activities, such as whether one frequents bars or transport hubs; major events; and school cycles.¹⁸ Police have sometimes used “furtive movements” as a basis for judging a potential target, and such behavior could also be detected through machine learning-based systems.¹⁹

Much of the technology employed in predictive policing has focused on expected crime locations, as “place-based crimes can be predicted because of the environmental vulnerabilities that encourage criminal activity.”²⁰ One example of a place-based crime prediction system is PredPol, a program that claimed to “predict, within a twelve-hour window, ‘where and when crimes [are] likely to occur’ using an algorithm that reviews ten years of ‘data, including the types of crimes and the dates, times and locations where they occurred.’”²¹

¹³ See generally Peter B. Hoffman et al., *Sentencing Reform, Sentencing Guidelines, and Related Issues: A Partial Bibliography*, 14 J. CRIM. JUST. 545 (1986); U.S. v. Booker, 543 U.S. 220 (2005).

¹⁴ Ignacio Cofone & Warut Khern-am-nuai, *The Overstated Cost of AI Fairness in Criminal Justice*, 100 INDIANA L.J. 1431 (2025); Sandra G. Mayson, *Dangerous Defendants*, 127 YALE L.J. 490, 493 (2018).

¹⁵ Dan Hunter et al., *A Framework for The Efficient and Ethical Use of Artificial Intelligence in the Criminal Justice System*, 47 FLA. ST. U. L. REV. 749, 762 (2020).

¹⁶ *Id.* at 765.

¹⁷ *Id.*

¹⁸ *Id.* See also Andrew G. Ferguson, *Policing Predictive Policing*, 94 WASH. U. L. REV. 1109, 1137 (2017) (providing “police departments gather and then collate crime data and use this to identify ‘crime hotspots’”).

¹⁹ Dan Hunter et al., *A Framework for The Efficient and Ethical Use of Artificial Intelligence in the Criminal Justice System*, 47 FLA. ST. U. L. REV. 749, 763 (2020) (stating these movements include “changing direction,” “walking in a certain way,” “acting a little suspicious,” “making a movement that is not regular,” being “very fidgety,” “going in and out of [one’s] pocket,” “going in and out of a location,” “looking back and forth constantly,” “looking over their shoulder,” “adjusting their hip or their belt,” “moving in and out of a car too quickly,” “turning a part of their body away from you,” “grabbing at a certain pocket or something at their waist,” “getting a little nervous, maybe shaking,” and “stuttering.”).

²⁰ Ferguson, *supra* note 18, at 1137.

²¹ Mirko Bagaric et al., *The Solution to the Pervasive Bias and Discrimination in the Criminal Justice System: Transparent and Fair Artificial Intelligence*, 59 AM. CRIM. L. REV. 95, 110 (2022) (quoting Mark Puente, *LAPD*

The objective of person-based prediction—the newer type of predictive policing—is to identify individuals likely to be involved in a crime before a crime occurs.²² Some common factors used in person-based algorithms are data taken from existing criminal records, associations, and trends in criminal activity. Officers can use predictive policing assessments when responding to emergencies to anticipate the likely risk associated with any alleged perpetrators.²³ There are various types of person-based prediction programs that differ in the algorithms they employ and the way they use the algorithm’s output predictions. Chicago police departments, for instance, have implemented the Crime and Victimization Risk Model which “assigns individuals a ‘score’ representing their likelihood of becoming involved with a violent crime.”²⁴ These scores are used to identify people at risk and plan “interventions” with social workers to help the individuals avoid crime; they also put the individuals on a “strategic subjects list” that rank them “according to their probability of being involved in a shooting or murder, either as a victim or an offender, known as a ‘Party to Violence’ (PTV).”²⁵ The algorithm that computes the scores draws from empirical data, including records of violence, rate and direction of criminal activities (escalation versus decline), and the details of the individuals’ criminal history.²⁶ Mapping the details enables police departments to use network analysis in examining connections between thousands of gang members, which then helps predict by whom and at what time a crime may occur.²⁷

BRT spans far more broadly than algorithmic sentencing and predictive policing. It involves the full range of governmental functions, from tax compliance and environmental protection to workplace safety and public benefits. While predictive policing scholarship has centered on Fourth Amendment concerns and discriminatory enforcement in criminal law enforcement, regulatory applications of algorithmic and AI-driven enforcement present more systematic questions for the entire legal process. Regulatory agencies must balance efficient resource allocation with maintaining public trust, foster voluntary compliance while protecting individual rights, and promote cooperation rather than merely deterring or averting violations.

Pioneered Predicting Crime with Data. Many Police Don't Think It Works, L.A. TIMES (July 3, 2019), <https://www.latimes.com/local/lanow/la-me-lapd-precision-policing-data-20190703-story.html>.

²² Namrata Kakade, Note, *Sloshing Through the Factbound Morass of Reasonableness: Predictive Algorithms, Racialized Policing, and Fourth Amendment Use of Force*, 88 GEO. WASH. L. REV. 788, 795 (2020).

²³ *Id.* at 796.

²⁴ Erik Bakke, *Predictive Policing: The Argument for Public Transparency*, 74 N.Y.U. ANN. SURV. AM. L. 131, 137 (2018).

²⁵ Ferguson, *supra* note 18, at 1139.

²⁶ *Id.*

²⁷ *Id.* at 1139–40.

B. *The Acceleration of AI Deployment in the Regulatory Process*

Slightly behind the private market, government agencies today are adopting AI models that analyze a wide range of data to assess the risk levels associated with organizations and individuals.²⁸ In 2020, 64 of the 142 federal departments, agencies, and sub-agencies had at least experimented with AI technology.²⁹ In 2023, a study by the Federal Government Accountability Office (GAO) reported about 1,200 current and planned AI use cases across twenty agencies—specific challenges or opportunities that AI may solve, including “analyzing data from cameras and radar to identify border activities, analyzing photographs from drones, and targeting of scientific specimens for planetary rovers.”³⁰ Since then, agency adoption of AI has been accelerating.³¹ Agencies are increasingly exploiting AI capabilities by creating models to enforce regulatory mandates, adjudicate government benefits, conduct research, monitor and analyze public health risks, extract information from big government data, and support various internal management processes that increase regulatory efficiency. These models consider factors such as financial stability, compliance history, legal records, consumption behavior, and more. By leveraging AI, governments can identify high-risk entities that may require closer monitoring or scrutiny. Conversely, governments can identify low-risk actors by relying on data points including personality characteristics and past behavior. AI can also analyze interconnected networks of companies, individuals, and transactions to identify relationships and patterns. For example, governments can gain insight into potential risks or fraudulent activities by examining financial transactions, business associations, travel and movement, consumption, social media engagement, and professional and social connections.³² Network analysis can help uncover hidden relationships, further facilitating the identification of high-risk and low-risk entities or individuals.³³ This ability to categorize actors is seen as a vital step toward creating a more efficient system of governance and, in the process, reforming the relationship between policymaking bodies, enforcement and regulation actors, and citizens.

However, agencies lack money, resources, and time. Compliance systems are notoriously under-resourced, and, given the Trump administration’s efforts to downsize the federal workforce, face a pronounced challenge to allocate enforcement resources more accurately and discriminately. Algorithms can help agencies make better use of their limited resources by identifying areas with

²⁸ Cary Coglianese & Orly Lobel, *Algorithmic Administration as Constitutional Governance*, in OXFORD HANDBOOK ON DIGITAL CONSTITUTIONALISM (Giovanni De Gregorio et al. eds., 2024).

²⁹ Gordon Unzen, Note, *Artificial Intelligence and the Administrative State: Regulating the Government Use of Decision-Making Technology*, 25 MINN. J. L. SCI. & TECH. 209, 235 (2023).

³⁰ U.S. GOV’T ACCOUNTABILITY OFF., GAO-24-105980, ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: AGENCIES HAVE BEGUN IMPLEMENTATION BUT NEED TO COMPLETE KEY REQUIREMENTS (2023).

³¹ See Coglianese & Lobel, *supra* note 28.

³² See e.g., Yogesh K. Dwivedi et al., *Setting the Future of Digital and Social Media Marketing Research: Perspectives and Research Propositions*, 59 INT’L J. OF INFO. MGMT. 1 (2021).

³³ *Id.*

higher chances of noncompliance, allowing them to prioritize their efforts more effectively. Large-data algorithms can analyze large amounts of data and identify patterns that humans may miss, providing insights that can aid in making more informed decisions related to compliance and enforcement. In a recent study, for instance, researchers used machine learning methods to estimate the effects of counterfactual targeting rules the Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) could deploy—that is, using automated analysis to help the agency decide how and which workplaces to inspect.³⁴ The study estimated that OSHA could have averted over twice as many injuries if its inspections targeted the establishments identified through machine learning methods; further, the study estimated that deploying such methods would have generated as much as \$876 million in social value over the decade examined.³⁵

Automation and digitization can also alleviate the burdens of administrative paperwork, which a 2021 Presidential Executive Order described as “in excess of 9 billion hours” annually.³⁶ Agencies including the Internal Revenue Service (IRS), Bureau of Labor Statistics (BLS), Social Security Administration (SSA), Customs and Border Protection (CBP), Food and Drug Administration (FDA), Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), Federal Communications Commission (FCC), and United States Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO) are now employing automated systems for tasks once performed by humans.³⁷ For example, the Department of Veterans Affairs uses AI in administering veteran benefits, while the Department of Education uses an automated chatbot to help navigate student loan applications.³⁸ The Department of Health and Human Services (HHS) has sponsored the creation of an AI-based tool to detect illegal opioid sellers.³⁹ The FDA has similarly used AI in criminal investigations and for mining online reports on unsafe food.⁴⁰ The IRS adopted AI early to predict potential violators of laws and regulations.⁴¹ CBP and the Transportation Security Administration (TSA) each deploy facial recognition and risk detection systems to identify security threats.⁴²

A particularly illustrative example of behavioral-recognition tools already deployed in federal regulatory practice is the IRS’s Return Review Program (RRP), a machine-learning

³⁴ See Matthew S. Johnson et al., *Improving Regulatory Effectiveness Through Better Targeting: Evidence from OSHA*, 15 AM. ECON. J.: APPLIED ECON. 30 (2023).

³⁵ *Id.* at 55–56.

³⁶ Exec. Order No. 14058, 86 Fed. Reg. 71357, 71357 (Dec. 13, 2021).

³⁷ Orly Lobel, *The Law of AI for Good*, 75 FLA. L. REV. 1073, 1104 (2023); DAVID FREEMAN ENGSTROM ET AL., GOVERNMENT BY ALGORITHM: ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN FEDERAL ADMINISTRATIVE AGENCIES: REPORT SUBMITTED TO THE ADMINISTRATIVE CONFERENCE OF THE UNITED STATES 21–69 (2020).

³⁸ ENGSTROM ET AL., *supra* note 37, at 37.

³⁹ *Id.* at 17.

⁴⁰ *Id.* at 54–55.

⁴¹ *Id.* at 27.

⁴² *Id.* at 10.

modernization of the agency's legacy Discriminant Function (DIF) scoring system.⁴³ Rather than relying exclusively on static return attributes or demographic proxies, the RRP analyzes dynamic behavioral signatures embedded in taxpayers' filing histories and refund claims, including year-over-year changes in withholding behavior, the sequencing of filings, anomalous timing characteristics of common refund-fraud schemes, and network connections to high-risk tax preparers or previously detected fraud rings. By modeling these behavioral patterns across millions of returns, the IRS generates individualized risk assessments that function in effect as trust predictions: returns with low behavioral-risk scores are processed with minimal intervention, while those with high-risk behavioral signatures are routed to more intensive review or audit. The system thereby replaces random or categorical audit triggers with a behavioral recognition model of compliance, embedding algorithmic trust judgments at the core of modern tax enforcement.

The EPA similarly relies on behavioral-recognition techniques to anticipate violations in environmental compliance regimes. In its advanced monitoring programs, the agency uses machine-learning models trained on historical enforcement data to identify facilities whose operational behaviors suggest a heightened probability of future violations.⁴⁴ These models integrate telemetry from continuous emissions monitors; remote-sensing data capturing physical activity inconsistent with permit terms; and "behavioral" compliance attributes, such as the timing, completeness, and strategic patterning of self-reported discharge data. Facilities that repeatedly submit reports immediately following known monitoring gaps, or that display atypical fluctuations in waste streams correlated with historically high-risk operational cycles, are flagged for unannounced inspections or enhanced oversight. In this way, the EPA has shifted from a static, paperwork-based conception of compliance toward a dynamic behavioral model in which regulated entities' operational signatures become predictors of trustworthiness, enabling more targeted and evidence-based enforcement.

Occupational safety regulators have also adopted behavioral-recognition frameworks to guide resource allocation and enforcement. OSHA's severe-injury reporting and predictive-analytics initiatives analyze employer-level behavioral patterns—including the frequency and quality of near-miss reports, scheduling anomalies indicative of understaffing, deviations in equipment-use telemetry, and inconsistencies in required safety-training cycles—to estimate the

⁴³ See *Tax Refund and Noncompliance: IRS Could Further Leverage the Return Review Program to Strengthen Tax Enforcement*, U.S. GOVERNMENT ACCOUNTABILITY OFFICE (GAO-18-544, July 2018), <https://www.gao.gov/assets/gao-18-544.pdf>.

⁴⁴ Rob Jordan, *Algorithmic Approaches for Assessing Pollution Reduction Policies can Reveal Shifts in Environmental Protection of Minority Communities*, STANFORD REPORT (Mar. 8, 2021), <https://law.stanford.edu/press/algorithmic-approaches-for-assessing-pollution-reduction-policies-can-reveal-shifts-in-environmental-protection-of-minority-communities-according-to-stanford-researchers/>.

probability of future workplace injuries and violations.⁴⁵ Employers demonstrating stable reporting practices, consistent remedial actions, and equipment-use patterns aligned with sectoral norms, are deemed comparatively lower risk and may receive fewer inspections or qualify for cooperative enforcement programs. By contrast, firms whose behavioral signatures mirror those observed in past incidents—such as sudden declines in injury reporting, cyclical spikes in machine utilization without corresponding maintenance logs, or irregularities in workforce turnover—are prioritized for proactive inspections. The system thus assigns de facto trust scores based on behavioral evidence, replacing generalized suspicion with individualized predictive models that enable regulators to intervene before accidents occur.

The SSA and the SEC each use AI in administrative processes, demonstrating both the potential and challenges of such shifts. The SSA uses AI to adjudicate disability benefit cases in three ways: (1) clustering together similar cases for more efficient and equitable decisions from administrative judges; (2) identifying cases that are likely to be full grants, thereby saving resources; and (3) flagging errors in draft decisions by administrative judges, which avoids costly appeals and reversals and improves decision consistency overall.⁴⁶ The first use employs a latent class model of AI that uses hearing-level information concerning the age of the claimant, functional impairments, state of origin, and more, to create the clusters.⁴⁷ The Appeals Council reported a 7% gain in productivity and 12.5% reduction in errors as a result of this early AI pilot program. The second use employs an AI model that uses information about medical history, treatment protocols, and medical symptoms to predict easy grants for state Quick Disability Determination administrator review. The most ambitious use of AI comes in the third application by the SSA; flagging errors in draft decisions. AI draws on decision trees and policies developed in the 1990s and uses structured input to adhere to the communicated policies.⁴⁸ Natural language processing (NLP) is then used to flag potential errors and inconsistencies in the drafts.⁴⁹

In financial markets, the SEC has long confronted the challenge of detecting misconduct concealed within vast volumes of trading activity, leading the agency to deploy sophisticated behavioral-recognition tools through its Market Abuse Unit and the Market Information Data Analytics System (MIDAS).⁵⁰ These systems analyze microsecond-level trading behaviors—such

⁴⁵ See Injury Tracking Application (ITA) Data: Establishment and Case Detail Work-Related Injury and Illness Data, U.S. DEP'T OF LAB., <https://www.osha.gov/Establishment-Specific-Injury-and-Illness-Data> (last visited Dec. 19, 2025).

⁴⁶ David Freeman Engstrom & Daniel E. Ho, *Algorithmic Accountability in the Administrative State*, 37 YALE J. REGUL. 800, 805 (2020).

⁴⁷ *Id.* at 811.

⁴⁸ *Id.*

⁴⁹ *Id.* at 812.

⁵⁰ MIDAS: Market Information Data Analytics System, U.S. SECURITIES & EXCHANGE COMM'N (June 28, 2024), <https://www.sec.gov/securities-topics/market-structure-analytics/midas-market-information-data-analytics-system>.

as repeated order placements and cancellations indicative of spoofing, coordinated multi-account trading patterns characteristic of pump-and-dump schemes, and anomalous accumulations or dispersals of positions prior to major corporate events—to identify behavioral signatures associated with insider trading and market manipulation. Importantly, the SEC’s models do not merely identify isolated anomalous transactions; they detect patterned behavior sequences that match known profiles of manipulative conduct. Traders and firms whose behavioral patterns consistently align with legitimate market-making or investment strategies are effectively deemed trustworthy and subject to lower degrees of scrutiny, while actors whose behavioral signatures align with those of past violators are escalated for investigation. Through this behavioral recognition architecture, securities regulation increasingly reflects an algorithmic trust framework grounded in pattern-based detection rather than purely transactional review. The SEC utilizes AI to help focus scarce agency investigative and enforcement resources by identifying high-risk individuals and entities.

The SEC deploys two complementary AI systems for insider trading detection.⁵¹ ARTEMIS (Advanced Relational Trading Enforcement Metrics Investigation System) analyzes patterns across a database of over six billion trading records, primarily targeting serial offenders. ATLAS (Abnormal Trading and Link Analysis System), a newer tool employing a one-class support vector machine model, focuses on identifying first-time violations. Neither system is fully automated; both require enforcement staff to flag suspected offenders before initiating targeted data collection. Another tool, the Corporate Issuer Risk Assessment (CIRA), flags suspicious filings based on historical datasets.⁵²

Taken together, these developments reveal a structural shift in contemporary regulation: Across agencies, AI is no longer confined to back-office efficiency gains but increasingly shapes how regulators prioritize scrutiny, allocate scarce resources, and differentiate between high- and low-risk actors. By embedding predictive assessments of compliance and trustworthiness into core administrative functions, agencies seek to govern more selectively, preemptively, and efficiently.

⁵¹ Mary Jo White, Chair, SEC, Remarks at the International Institute for Securities Market Growth and Development (Apr. 8, 2016), <https://www.sec.gov/newsroom/speeches-statements/statement-mjw-040816>; Daniel M. Hawke, *SEC Data Analysis in Insider Trading Investigations*, CLS BLUE SKY BLOG (Aug. 21, 2019), <https://clsbluesky.law.columbia.edu/2019/08/21/sec-data-analysis-in-insider-trading-investigations/>.

⁵² ENGSTROM ET AL., *supra* note 37, at 23.

II. THE (DIS)TRUSTING REGULATORY STATE

A. *The Shift Toward Flexible Modes of Regulation*

Agencies have been experimenting with a shift from rigid, command-and-control frameworks toward flexible, context-specific compliance strategies for decades, well before the current AI revolution.⁵³ Programs like the EPA’s Audit Policy, which, between 1995-2000, has prompted over ten thousand entities to self-report and correct environmental violations in exchange for penalty reductions, illustrate the efficacy of trust-based mechanisms.⁵⁴ The IRS’s Compliance Assurance Process (CAP) further demonstrates this approach, with participating corporations pledging transparency for real-time tax guidance, which reduces uncertainty.⁵⁵ Similarly, the FDA’s Voluntary Qualified Importer Program (VQIP) expedites food imports for international firms with proven safety records.⁵⁶ The SEC’s Cooperation Program enhances enforcement by incentivizing self-reported securities violations.⁵⁷

Similarly, Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) policies are increasingly based on systems of self-reporting for companies to disclose their emissions and waste management practices.⁵⁸ Consider the Artificial Intelligence Environmental Impacts Act of 2024, an environmental AI-related bill introduced by Senator Edward Markey that exemplifies this idea of company self-reporting. The bill directs a consortium led by the Director of the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) to create a voluntary reporting system for AI developers and operators to utilize in reporting the environmental impacts of AI.⁵⁹

These initiatives reveal that well-designed trust-based tools—combining automated screening with relational strategies—can advance an agency’s instrumental aims and normative goals.⁶⁰ At the same time, voluntary self-reporting creates a regulatory dilemma: regulators must decide whether to trust companies to accurately and honestly report their environmental impact.

⁵³ See CASS R. SUNSTEIN, *RISK AND REASON: SAFETY, LAW, AND THE ENVIRONMENT* 45–47 (2002) (discussing the evolution from amongst regulatory agencies toward trust-based frameworks).

⁵⁴ See U.S. Env’t Prot. Agency, Off. of Enf’t & Compliance, 310F21001, *EPA Celebrates Key Anniversaries by Releasing Updated Audit Policy FAQs 2* (March 2021), <https://www.epa.gov/sites/default/files/2021-03/documents/auditpolicyprogramspotlight.pdf>.

⁵⁵ See *Compliance Assurance Process*, INTERNAL REVENUE SERV. (Aug. 22, 2025), <https://www.irs.gov/businesses/corporations/compliance-assurance-process> (describing CAP’s structure and benefits).

⁵⁶ See *Voluntary Qualified Importer Program (VQIP)*, U.S. FOOD & DRUG ADMIN. (2022), <https://www.fda.gov/food/importing-food-products-united-states/voluntary-qualified-importer-program-vqip>.

⁵⁷ See *Benefits of Cooperation With the Division of Enforcement*, U.S. SEC. & EXCHANGE COMM. (Sept. 15, 2025), <https://www.sec.gov/about/divisions-offices/division-enforcement/benefits-cooperation-division-enforcement#cooperation>.

⁵⁸ Virginia Harper Ho, *Modernizing ESG Disclosure*, UNIV. OF ILL. L. REV. 277 (2022).

⁵⁹ Artificial Intelligence Environmental Impacts Act of 2024, S. 3732, 118th Cong. (2024).

⁶⁰ See JOHN BRAITHWAITE, *RESTORATIVE JUSTICE AND RESPONSIVE REGULATION* 88–90 (2002) (arguing for regulatory designs that blend enforcement with trust-building).

This approach can be cost effective and encourage corporate responsibility.⁶¹ However, there is a risk that some companies might underreport their emissions or environmental violations to avoid penalties or negative publicity. This could lead to significant environmental harm going undetected.⁶²

Ultimately, trust-based programs depend on accurate predictions. The FDA employs this approach in its food safety oversight: restaurants with consistent health code compliance face reduced inspection frequency, easing regulatory burdens while safeguarding public health.⁶³ Yet, the 2015 Chipotle E. coli outbreak, which sickened dozens across multiple states, underscores the risks of this model when trust is misplaced.⁶⁴ The SEC also balances trust and oversight in securities regulation, offering leniency to firms in voluntary disclosure programs—but as seen in the 2008 financial crisis, the SEC also faces stark reminders of the perils of excessive reliance on self-regulation.⁶⁵ This regulatory dynamic exemplifies a broader “social capital paradox,” where trust lowers transaction costs and encourages voluntary compliance but, if abused, precipitates significant societal harm.⁶⁶ And yet, these trends indicate a growing reliance upon a new approach that contrasts with traditional command-and-control regulatory methods. To be more effective, these newer regulatory models require regulators to carefully consider and differentiate between the individuals and organizations they regulate and assess how different regulatees would respond to various signals, nudges, and incentives during policy implementation. These approaches inherently calibrate governmental trust in regulatees according to their demonstrated knowledge, integrity, and transparency.

These recent approaches have received a broad umbrella of terms in legal scholarship, including “new governance,”⁶⁷ “responsive regulation,”⁶⁸ “trust-based regulation,” behavior-based

⁶¹ Matthew Potoski & Aseem Prakash, *The Regulation Dilemma: Cooperation and Conflict in Environmental Governance*, 64 PUB. ADMIN. REV. 152 (2004).

⁶² Jodi L. Short & Michael W. Toffel, *Coerced Confessions: Self-Policing in the Shadow of the Regulator*, 24 J. L., ECON., & ORG. 45 (2008).

⁶³ See FDA Food Safety Modernization Act, H.R. 2751, 111th Cong. § 201(a) (2011) (codified as amended at 21 U.S.C. § 350j(a)(1)) (outlining risk-based inspection frequencies tied to factors including compliance history).

⁶⁴ See *Multistate Outbreak of E. coli O157 Infections Linked to Chipotle Mexican Grill Restaurants*, CTRS. FOR DISEASE CONTROL & PREVENTION (Dec. 8, 2015), <https://www.cdc.gov/ecoli/2015/o157h7-11-15/index.html>.

⁶⁵ See Fin. Crisis Inquiry Comm’n, *The Financial Crisis Inquiry Report* 188–92 (2011) (detailing failures of self-regulation in the lead-up to the 2008 crisis).

⁶⁶ See ROBERT D. PUTNAM, *BOWLING ALONE: THE COLLAPSE AND REVIVAL OF AMERICAN COMMUNITY* 135–36 (2000) (introducing the concept of social capital and its dual potential for benefit and harm).

⁶⁷ Lobel, *supra* note 9, at 344–350; Orly Lobel, *New Governance as Regulatory Governance*, in *THE OXFORD HANDBOOK OF GOVERNANCE* 65–82 (2012).

⁶⁸ AYRES & BRAITHWAITE, *supra* note 9; Christine Parker, *Twenty Years of Responsive Regulation: An Appreciation and Appraisal*, 7 REG. & GOVERNANCE 2 (2013).

regulation,⁶⁹ “self-regulation,”⁷⁰ and “personalized law.”⁷¹ Each term may convey slightly different attitudes, but the general concept is the same: regulatory agencies should abandon the universal distrust of their regulatory subjects in favor of more nuanced, differential treatment. This new regulatory paradigm hinges on the government’s ability to make valid predictions about varying levels of voluntary compliance—essentially, to determine whom to trust. This creates a fundamental dilemma: either invest in resource-intensive auditing of everyone to ensure that trust is not exploited or implement differential treatment of similarly situated regulatees based on trustworthiness assessments before violations occur. Differentiated treatment means deploying predictive enforcement, which puts more pressure on agencies to leverage data and technology in such a novel regulatory ecosystem.

B. Regulation and Trust

1. A Symbiotic Relationship

Although conventional discourse about the impact of regulation on market dynamics often ignores the role of trust,⁷² a nuanced analysis of current regulatory methods reveals a deeply interconnected relationship between control and trust.⁷³ Both regulation and trust emerge as important components within the broader framework of market dynamics, and their symbiotic relationship contributes significantly to shaping market performance.⁷⁴ Recent scholarship in regulatory compliance rejects the old deterrence-only paradigm and emphasizes that authority and trust operate together. In Erich Kirchler’s seminal *slippery slope* model, compliance depends on two dimensions: enforcement power and citizens’ trust in authorities.⁷⁵ Heavy enforcement alone (the “stick”) produces only enforced compliance, whereas high trust (the “carrot”) cultivates voluntary compliance.⁷⁶ Tom Tyler similarly observed that when authorities are seen as legitimate

⁶⁹ Eyal Peer & Yuval Feldman, *Honesty Pledges for the Behaviorally-Based Regulation of Dishonesty*, 28 J. EUR. PUB. POL’Y 761 (2021).

⁷⁰ CHRISTINE PARKER, *THE OPEN CORPORATION: EFFECTIVE SELF-REGULATION AND DEMOCRACY* (2002).

⁷¹ Christoph Busch, *Implementing Personalized Law: Personalized Disclosures in Consumer Law and Data Privacy Law*, 86 U. CHI. L. REV. 309 (2019).

⁷² Avishai Benish & David Levi-Faur, *The Expansion of Regulation in Welfare Governance*, ANNALS OF THE AM. ACADEMY OF POL. & SOCIAL SCIENCE 17–29 (2020).

⁷³ Frédérique Six & Koen Verhoest, *Trust in Regulatory Regimes: Scoping the Field*, in TRUST IN REGULATORY REGIMES (Frédérique Six & Koen Verhoest eds., 2017); Nicholas Charron et al., *Trust, Regulation, and Redistribution: Why Some Governments Overregulate and Under-Redistribute*, 15 REG. & GOVERNANCE 3 (2021).

⁷⁴ Paul S. Adler, *Market, Hierarchy, and Trust: The Knowledge Economy and the Future of Capitalism*, 12 ORG. SCI. 99 (2001). See also Libby Maman et al., *Varieties of Regulatory Regimes and their Effect on Citizens’ Trust in Firms*, 30 J. EURO. PUB. POL’Y 2807 (2023).

⁷⁵ Erich Kirchler et al., *Enforced versus Voluntary Tax Compliance: The “Slippery Slope” Framework*, 29 J. ECON. PSYCH. 210, 211–15 (2008).

⁷⁶ Stephan Muehlbacher et al., *Voluntary versus Enforced Tax Compliance: Empirical Evidence for the “Slippery Slope” Framework*, 32 EUR. J. L. & ECON. 89, 91–94 (2011); see also, e.g., Yuval Feldman, *The State’s Relationship*

and competent, people feel obligated to obey rules.⁷⁷ Thus, even in U.S. law enforcement and public administration, enhancing perceptions of fairness and service can boost compliance. Empirical studies confirm this synergy. In controlled experiments, taxpayers paid more when authorities were both powerful and trustworthy.⁷⁸ In one pair of studies, high trust raised voluntary tax payments, while high coercive power only raised payments when taxpayers were coerced.⁷⁹ Likewise, a 2024 IRS survey found that “fear of an audit” was only the sixth (out of eight) compliance motivator and that taxpayers with greater trust in the IRS were significantly more likely to obey tax laws.⁸⁰ Trust matters in domains beyond taxation as well. For example, high social trust has been shown to increase compliance with environmental regulations.⁸¹ These findings suggest that regulatory strategies combining credible enforcement with legitimacy-building policies like transparent processes and fair treatment are most effective at securing lasting compliance.⁸²

Subsequent studies advance these understandings by suggesting that regulatory oversight and trust-based strategies ought not be understood as alternatives but as complementary mechanisms.⁸³ As regulation scholar Frédérique Six argues, responsive regulation theory attains its greatest efficacy when it calibrates and integrates both trust and control, allowing for oversight rooted in cooperation rather than suspicion. This insight challenges binary frameworks and instead advocates for regulatory designs that dynamically blend credible oversight with efforts to foster trust. Empirical studies further substantiate these claims. In a classic study on trust and regulation, Braithwaite and Makkai found that compliance improves when regulators treat industry managers as trustworthy, suggesting that trust fosters voluntary adherence to regulation.⁸⁴ Verhoest et al. further examined trust’s role in regulatory performance and legitimacy through cross-country survey data.⁸⁵ Their research similarly showed that a “watchful trust” approach enhances

with Its Citizens: From Coercion to Compliance and Back 22–23 (Bar Ilan Univ. Fac. L. Rsch. Paper No. 5967915, 2025), <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5967915>.

⁷⁷ TOM R. TYLER, *WHY PEOPLE OBEY THE LAW* 45–68 (2006).

⁷⁸ Muehlbacher et al., *supra* note 76, at 95–96.

⁷⁹ *Id.*

⁸⁰ INTERNAL REVENUE SERV., PUB. NO. 5296, *COMPREHENSIVE TAXPAYER ATTITUDE SURVEY (CTAS) 2024* (2024).

⁸¹ Søren C. Winter & Peter J. May, *Motivation for Compliance with Environmental Regulations*, 20 *J. POL’Y ANALYSIS & MGMT.* 675, 690–94 (2001); *see also* Yasir Shahab et al., *Social Trust, Environmental Violations, and Remedial Actions in China*, 198 *J. BUS. ETHICS* 637 (2025) (using unique environmental violation data from China spanning 2007–2022, this study finds that social trust significantly reduces firms’ propensity to commit environmental violations and motivates them to engage in restorative remedial actions, demonstrating that informal social constraints can be as effective as formal regulatory measures in promoting environmental compliance).

⁸² Kirchler et al., *supra* note 75, at 220–24; Muehlbacher et al., *supra* note 76, at 96–97.

⁸³ Frédérique Six, *Trust in Regulatory Relations*, 15 *PUB. MGMT. REV.* 163, 165–170 (2013).

⁸⁴ John Braithwaite & Toni Makkai, *Trust and Compliance*, 4 *POLICING & SOC’Y* 1 (1994).

⁸⁵ Koen Verhoest et al., *How Trust Matters for the Performance and Legitimacy of Regulatory Regimes: The Differential Impact of Watchful Trust and Good-Faith Trust*, 19 *REG. & GOVERNANCE* 3 (2025).

regulatory compliance.⁸⁶ However, their findings suggest a fundamental tension. While verification improves performance, excessive oversight can undermine legitimacy by fostering suspicion and eroding shared norms.⁸⁷ Together, this body of scholarship maps how regulatory design grounded in both authority and trust can increase not only compliance rates but also deeper forms of legitimacy, offering crucial lessons for the evolving landscape of data-driven, AI-enabled regulation.

Trust in governmental institutions and regulatory bodies is thus a critical determinant of overall market functionality.⁸⁸ A high level of trust instills confidence in market participants, fostering an environment conducive to efficient economic transactions and cooperative interactions. But for trust-based regulation to work, all actors in the regulatory ecosystem—states, corporate actors, and stakeholders—must be able to trust each other.

2. Self-Regulation and Trust

As a regulatory approach, self-regulation offers entities enhanced flexibility in establishing objectives and developing strategies for their attainment.⁸⁹ This paradigm relies on indirect oversight from both governmental and private entities, with diverse actors—rather than a centralized or public authority—participating in various regulatory tasks, including rule-setting, monitoring, and enforcement.⁹⁰

The COVID-19 pandemic, for example, presented regulatory authorities with complex decisions about trust-based versus command-and-control approaches to health and safety protocols, particularly regarding public health compliance monitoring in educational settings.⁹¹ Consider health screenings for schoolchildren: some jurisdictions implemented trust-based systems whereby parents pledged to monitor their children’s temperatures and COVID-19 status, while others adopted direct surveillance methods through on-site temperature checks. The efficacy of these divergent approaches raises empirical and normative questions about both compliance prediction and equity. From an empirical perspective, regulators must evaluate the likelihood of compliance across different populations and institutional settings. This involves analyzing whether

⁸⁶ *Id.* at 8, 12 (finding support for the hypothesis that “the perceived performance of a given regulatory regime should be enhanced when actors are able to balance trust and watchfulness”).

⁸⁷ *Id.* at 8 (“high levels of watchfulness [...] could actually erode the long-term acceptance of a given regulatory regime, as it implies continuous suspicion-based vigilance and negative expectations of harmful actions by the other actor”).

⁸⁸ Charron et al., *supra* note 73.

⁸⁹ Ian Bartle & Peter Vass, *Self-Regulation Within the Regulatory State: Towards a New Regulatory Paradigm?*, 85 PUB. ADMIN. 885 (2007).

⁹⁰ Anil K. Gupta & Lawrence J. Lad, *Industry Self-Regulation: An Economic, Organizational, and Political Analysis*, 8 ACAD. MGMT. REV. 416 (1983).

⁹¹ *Compare with* YUVAL FELDMAN, CAN THE PUBLIC BE TRUSTED?: ON THE PROMISE AND PERILS OF VOLUNTARY COMPLIANCE 1–31 (2025).

particular demographics or school communities demonstrate higher rates of adherence to self-reporting requirements. For example, a Canadian study found that people with antisocial personality traits (such as “Machiavellianism”) were consistently associated with lower compliance in COVID-19 public health measures.⁹² In contrast, a Brazilian study found that people with traits such as honesty, humility, and openness demonstrated higher compliance levels.⁹³ An Italian study similarly found that personality traits significantly influenced responses to public health messaging: individuals higher in emotionality demonstrated increased compliance, while those scoring higher on Machiavellianism showed decreased compliance.⁹⁴ These findings underscore the potential of personalized messaging, tailored to individual characteristics that predict compliance behavior, to enhance regulatory and enforcement efficacy.

The normative dimension presents more challenging questions about the ethics of differential trust in regulatory design. In successful self-regulatory regimes, a harmonious relationship is cultivated between the regulator and the regulatee.⁹⁵ While self-regulation often emerges voluntarily as firms collaborate to manage collective behavior,⁹⁶ it can also be mandated through governmental regulatory design.⁹⁷ But a significant aspect of this regulatory approach hinges on the confidence that individuals will conduct themselves in a trustworthy manner. This presents a potential vulnerability: without a clear understanding of whom to trust, self-regulation could potentially become a haven for those seeking to exploit the trust placed in them by authorities. At the same time, rejecting differential trust frameworks may result in universal distrust, potentially imposing greater burdens on all populations through enhanced direct surveillance. This regulatory dilemma illustrates broader tensions between administrative efficiency, equity, and privacy in public health governance. The choice between trust-based and command-and-control approaches requires balancing competing values while acknowledging the practical limitations of each regulatory model.

⁹² Julie Blais et al., *Who Complies and Who Defies? Personality and Public Health Compliance*, 3 FRONTIERS POL. SCI. 1, 2–3 (2021).

⁹³ See Fabiano Koich Miguel et al., *Compliance with Containment Measures to the COVID-19 Pandemic over Time: Do Antisocial Traits Matter?*, 168 PERSONALITY & INDIVIDUAL DIFFERENCES 1 (2021) (detailing a sample from Brazil during COVID-19).

⁹⁴ Paolo Roma et al., *How to Improve Compliance with Protective Health Measures During the COVID-19 Outbreak: Testing a Moderated Mediation Model and Machine Learning Algorithms*, 17 INT’L J. ENV’T RSCH. & PUB. HEALTH 1 (2020).

⁹⁵ Cary Coglianese & Evan Mendelson, *Meta-Regulation and Self-Regulation*, in THE OXFORD HANDBOOK OF REG. 146–68 (Robert Baldwin et al. eds., 2010).

⁹⁶ Frances Bowen, *Marking Their Own Homework: The Pragmatic and Moral Legitimacy of Industry Self-Regulation*, 156 J. BUS. ETHICS 257 (2019).

⁹⁷ Julia Black, *Decentring Regulation: Understanding the Role of Regulation and Self-Regulation in a ‘Post-Regulatory’ World*, 54 CURRENT LEGAL PROBS. 103 (2001).

3. Pledges and Trust

A central BRT incorporated by regulatory agencies in diverse contexts is the pledging mechanism. Under the pledging mechanism, regulatory actors affirm their ex ante commitment to full compliance. In return, the regulatory actors receive light enforcement burdens.⁹⁸ Pledging mechanisms are a more flexible regulatory approach because they do not require people to provide evidence supporting their promises to comply. Honesty pledges are understood to mitigate moral disengagement in the face of ethical dilemmas, fostering increased honesty in reporting or behavior.⁹⁹ Their efficacy lies in heightening the awareness of ethics, making it challenging for individuals to dismiss or rationalize unethical actions.¹⁰⁰ In turn, by integrating such voluntary commitments into their enforcement strategies, administrative agencies can potentially enhance their regulatory effectiveness while reducing reliance on traditional command-and-control measures.

A recent study found that honesty pledges are an effective tool for regulating behavior, significantly reducing dishonesty in both one-time and sequential decision-making contexts without diminishing effectiveness over time or with repeated exposure.¹⁰¹ Importantly, pledges remained effective even in the presence of monetary incentives for dishonesty.¹⁰² The research suggests that pledges primarily work by reducing ambiguity about expected behavior, rather than merely serving as moral reminders.¹⁰³ These findings have important implications for trust and regulation. Pledges can serve as a trust-building mechanism between regulators and regulatees, potentially offering an alternative to more invasive monitoring techniques. This approach

⁹⁸ Honesty pledges extend beyond signature attestations in several U.S. professional licensing contexts. See FLA. BAR, OATH OF ADMISSION TO THE FLORIDA BAR (2011), <https://www-media.floridabar.org/uploads/2017/04/oath-of-admission-to-the-florida-bar-ada.pdf> (requiring attorneys to “employ... such means only as are consistent with truth and honor, and... never seek to mislead the judge or jury by any artifice or false statement”); Attorney Oath of Admission, COLO. SUP. CT. OFF. OF ATT’Y REGUL. COUNS., <https://www.coloradolegalregulation.com/current-lawyers/oath/> (pledging to “treat all persons... with fairness, courtesy, respect and honesty”). The National Association of REALTORS® requires members to recite the REALTOR® Pledge, committing to “be honorable” and “honest[] in all real estate dealings.” NAT’L ASS’N OF REALTORS, THE REALTOR PLEDGE (1954, rev. mid-1990s), <https://www.nar.realtor/sites/default/files/applications-and-forms/2013/PledgeRevised.pdf>. For a comprehensive international example, see *About the Banker’s Oath*, FOUNDATION FOR BANKING ETHICS ENFORCEMENT, <https://www.tuchtrechtbanken.nl/en/about-the-bankers-oath/> (mandating all 66,000 Dutch bank employees pledge to “act openly and accountably” and “make every effort to improve and retain trust in the financial sector”). See also Peer & Feldman, *supra* note 69.

⁹⁹ Albert Bandura, *Human Agency in Social Cognitive Theory*, 44 AM. PSYCH. 1175 (1989); Albert Bandura, *Mechanisms of Moral Disengagement*, in ORIGINS OF TERRORISM: PSYCHOLOGIES, IDEOLOGIES, THEOLOGIES, STATES OF MIND 161 (Walter Reich ed., 1990).

¹⁰⁰ Jason Dana, et al., *Exploiting Moral Wiggle Room: Experiments Demonstrating an Illusory Preference for Fairness*, 33 ECON. THEORY 67 (2007); Shaul Shalvi et al., *Self-Serving Justifications: Doing Wrong and Feeling Moral*, 24 CURRENT DIRECTIONS PSYCH. SCI. 125 (2015).

¹⁰¹ Peer & Feldman, *supra* note 69, at 774.

¹⁰² *Id.* at 774–775.

¹⁰³ *Id.* at 777.

demonstrates the value of incorporating behavioral insights into regulatory strategies, moving beyond traditional deterrence-based approaches. The broad effectiveness of pledges across different individuals suggests the pledges could be a useful tool in addressing the challenge of heterogeneity in compliance motivations within a population.

Still, pledges do not eliminate the need for verification entirely. As Hilo-Merkovich and colleagues show, individuals are required to make declarations affirming the accuracy and honesty of their submissions in routine activities like applying for permits or benefits from the state and in insurance claims.¹⁰⁴ They note that while these declarations are intended to foster ethical conduct, relying solely on such declarations without complementary monitoring and auditing presents an opportunity for self-serving false claims.¹⁰⁵ Consequently, it becomes imperative for regulators and policymakers to empirically understand the extent to which pledges effectively deter unethical behavior.¹⁰⁶

4. Determinants of Regulatory Trust: Past Behavior, Cross-Domain

Trust-based regulatory technologies are highly appealing, as they reduce auditing and enforcement costs while simultaneously strengthening social capital and boosting economic performance. However, these advantages face a central functional challenge that reflects the fundamental realization driving personalization in regulation and enforcement generally: *regulatory subjects vary in the extent to which they can be trusted*. A variety of personal, cultural, professional, and ideological constraints on regulatory trustworthiness apply differentially to different regulatory subjects in different regulatory domains. This means that governments are unable to use trust-based programs without employing costly oversight mechanisms to identify untrustworthy actors. Getting a better sense, *ex ante*, of who can be trusted with their pledges is hence likely to dramatically improve the efficacy of these programs. This understanding motivates the development and deployment of AI-powered data-based BRT algorithms as a central feature of new regulatory approaches, while at the same time invoking a host of new normative challenges.

Current AI-powered systems employ several sophisticated approaches to infer trustworthiness across domains. In this endeavor, behavioral pattern analysis serves as the primary

¹⁰⁴ Rinat Hilo-Merkovich et al., *Affidavit Aversion: Public Preferences for Trust-Based Policy Instruments*, 18 REG. & GOVERNANCE 970, 971 (2024).

¹⁰⁵ *Id.* at 973.

¹⁰⁶ See, e.g., YUVAL FELDMAN, *THE LAW OF GOOD PEOPLE: CHALLENGING STATES' ABILITY TO REGULATE HUMAN BEHAVIOR* (2018).

methodology, examining individual compliance history, decision-making patterns, and behavioral consistency across different regulatory contexts.¹⁰⁷

The emerging framework of “personalized enforcement” has captured this evolution from uniform regulatory application toward differentiated compliance assessment grounded in behavioral science—a development that both instantiates and extends the personalized law theory articulated by Ariel Porat and Omri Ben-Shahar.¹⁰⁸ Where traditional enforcement applies identical scrutiny across regulated entities, regardless of their demonstrated compliance trajectories, personalized enforcement leverages algorithmic analysis to calibrate regulatory attention according to entity-specific *behavioral* characteristics, transforming enforcement from crude demographic profiling or arbitrary uniformity into what might be termed the “reasonable you” standard based on actual conduct.¹⁰⁹ This approach finds concrete expression in the coordinated federal enforcement initiatives announced by the Federal Trade Commission (FTC), Department of Justice (DOJ), Consumer Financial Protection Bureau (CFPB), and Equal Employment Opportunity Commission (EEOC), which collectively committed to deploying algorithmic tools to identify patterns of violations and compliance, creating enforcement systems that reward demonstrated trustworthiness while targeting persistent violators.¹¹⁰ The Federation of American Scientists’ proposal to modernize Title VI enforcement exemplifies this behaviorally-

¹⁰⁷ See U.S. DEP’T OF COMM., ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE RISK MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORK (AI RMF 1.0) 9–12 (2023) (establishing characteristics of trustworthy AI systems including validation through behavioral assessment, accountability metrics, and reliability measures across different operational contexts).

¹⁰⁸ See Omri Ben-Shahar & Ariel Porat, *Personalizing Negligence Law*, 91 N.Y.U. L. REV. 627, 627–28 (2016) (arguing that “with the increasing availability of information about actors’ characteristics, negligence law should give up much of its objectivity by allowing courts to ‘subjectify’ the standard of care—that is, to tailor it to the specific injurer’s tendency to create risks and his or her ability to reduce them”) [hereinafter *Negligence*]; OMRI BEN-SHAHAR & ARIEL PORAT, *PERSONALIZED LAW: DIFFERENT RULES FOR DIFFERENT PEOPLE* (2021) (providing a comprehensive theoretical framework for personalized legal rules that prioritize individual behavioral data) [hereinafter *Personalized Law*].

¹⁰⁹ *Negligence*, *supra* note 108, at 636–46 (developing the “reasonable you” concept as a replacement for the uniform “reasonable person” standard, accounting for individual risk propensity and demonstrated skill levels based on behavioral evidence); see also Paul Gendreau et al., *A Meta-Analysis of the Predictors of Adult Offender Recidivism: What Works!*, 34 CRIMINOLOGY 575, 582 (1996) (finding criminal history—a behavioral indicator—to be among the strongest predictors of future behavior, with effect sizes substantially larger than demographic variables).

¹¹⁰ See Lina M. Khan, *Joint Statement on Enforcement Efforts Against Discrimination and Bias in Automated Systems*, FED. TRADE COMM’N (Apr. 25, 2023), <https://www.ftc.gov/legal-library/browse/cases-proceedings/public-statements/joint-statement-enforcement-efforts-against-discrimination-bias-automated-systems>; Jason D. Krieser & Shawn C. Helms, *US Federal Agencies Commit to Regulatory Enforcement of AI Systems*, MCDERMOTT WILL & SCHULTE (May 31, 2023), <https://www.mwe.com/insights/us-federal-agencies-commit-to-regulatory-enforcement-of-ai-systems/> (analyzing how the joint statement emphasizes pattern identification and behavioral assessment rather than demographic profiling).

grounded approach, recommending context-specific frameworks that assess actual algorithmic outcomes and institutional practices rather than relying on demographic proxies.¹¹¹

This methodology operationalizes Ben-Shahar and Porat’s concepts of “detection-based personalization” and “benefit-based personalization,” wherein enforcement intensity and sanctions vary according to individualized behavioral patterns, an approach validated by extensive social psychological research demonstrating that past behavior remains among the most robust predictors of future conduct.¹¹² Crucially, as Porat and Strahilevitz observe, such data-driven behavioral personalization offers superior fairness compared to discretionary enforcement systems historically susceptible to implicit bias, precisely because it grounds enforcement decisions in objective behavioral indicators rather than immutable demographic characteristics.¹¹³ By prioritizing individual conduct over group membership, personalized enforcement systems can enhance regulatory effectiveness by directing scarce resources toward demonstrated risks and advance equality by avoiding the demographic stereotyping that has plagued traditional enforcement regimes.¹¹⁴

Predictive behavioral modeling thus leverages past compliance behavior as a key predictor of future compliance behavior, though this predictive power varies significantly across different

¹¹¹ Alejandro Jimenez Jaramillo, *Modernizing Enforcement of the Civil Rights Act to Mitigate Algorithmic Harm in Determining Federal Benefits*, FED’N OF AM. SCIENTISTS (Mar. 1, 2023), <https://fas.org/publication/modernizing-enforcement-of-the-civil-rights-act-to-mitigate-algorithmic-harm-in-determining-federal-benefits/> (proposing frameworks that focus on documented discriminatory outcomes and institutional practices, behavioral evidence, rather than demographic composition of affected populations).

¹¹² *Personalized Law*, *supra* note 101 (distinguishing between “detection-based personalization,” which tailors enforcement based on individual compliance history, and “benefit-based personalization,” which adjusts sanctions based on demonstrated patterns of benefit from violations); *see also* Walter Mischel & Yuichi Shoda, *A Cognitive-Affective System Theory of Personality: Reconceptualizing Situations, Dispositions, Dynamics, and Invariance in Personality Structure*, 102 PSYCH. REV. 246 (1995) (providing theoretical foundation for behavioral consistency across situations); Denise de Ridder & John de Wit, *Self-Regulation in Health Behavior: Concepts, Theories, and Central Issues*, in SELF-REGUL. IN HEALTH BEHAV. 1, 5–8 (Denise de Ridder & John de Wit eds., 2006) (reviewing evidence that past self-regulatory behavior predicts future behavior).

¹¹³ Ariel Porat & Lior J. Strahilevitz, *Personalizing Default Rules and Disclosure with Big Data*, 112 MICH. L. REV. 1417, 1420–22, 1454–56 (2014) (explaining that “systematic, algorithmic personalization based on behavioral data reduces the scope for implicit bias compared to discretionary enforcement systems” and noting that “behavioral variables are both more predictive and less morally problematic than demographic variables”); *see also* Omri Ben-Shahar & Ariel Porat, *How to Evaluate Personalized Law*, UNIV. CHI. L. REV. (2022), <https://lawreview.uchicago.edu/online-archive/how-evaluate-personalized-law> (observing that data-guided personalization can “replace opaque discretion with transparent, auditable decision-making”).

¹¹⁴ *See* Reuben Binns, *Fairness in Machine Learning: Lessons from Political Philosophy*, 81 PROC. MACH. LEARNING RSCH. 1, 7 (2018) (arguing that holding individuals accountable for their choices and conduct rather than immutable characteristics aligns with egalitarian principles); *cf.* Sandra G. Mayson, *Bias In, Bias Out*, 128 YALE L.J. 2218, 2220–25 (2019) (demonstrating that demographic variables in predictive tools often serve as proxies for systemic disadvantage, while behavioral variables reflect individual choices).

regulatory domains.¹¹⁵ Cross-domain behavioral inference allows AI systems to identify how seemingly unrelated behaviors like tax compliance patterns, workplace conduct, or consumer behavior can predict regulatory compliance in entirely different contexts.¹¹⁶ This idea of differentiated treatment of infractions and potential future risks is not, in itself, a new realization. Any allocation of limited enforcement resources involves some discrimination among subjects based on an estimation of the likelihood of violation under varying conditions. However, while human discretion in allocating enforcement resources is already subject to normative evaluation and legal regulation despite its fallibilities and biases,¹¹⁷ use of AI presents undertheorized normative challenges, particularly regarding algorithmic bias and fairness in automated decision-making systems.¹¹⁸ We address these challenges in Part III.

III. BEHAVIORAL RECOGNITION TECHNOLOGY AND IMPACT ON RIGHTS AND INTERESTS

Given differential levels of trustworthiness among regulatory subjects, regulators deploying BRT will necessarily distinguish among regulated entities. The trusting state is thus, ipso facto, also the *distrusting* state; differentiating between trusted and distrusted actors becomes a central function of new regulatory regimes.¹¹⁹ The use of AI in regulatory trust differentiation can impact both individual rights and public interests. We discuss each impact in detail below, distinguishing between the various rights that could be implicated by AI-driven BRT, as well as analyzing possible externalities that such technologies could create.

A. Rights

1. Privacy

Facial recognition has dominated debates over algorithmic governance, prompting bans across jurisdictions.¹²⁰ Yet this controversy captures only part of the challenge. Unlike biometric

¹¹⁵ See, e.g., Gendreau et al., *supra* note 109 (positing criminal history as a strong predictor of future criminal behavior); Miyuki Hino et al., *Machine Learning for Environmental Monitoring*, 1 NATURE SUSTAINABILITY 583 (2018) (using past violations as an important factor in the machine-learning model predicting the failure and success rates of future facility inspections).

¹¹⁶ See, e.g., *Negligence*, *supra* note 108, at 679; Busch, *supra* note 71, at 329. *But see* Jordan M. Barry et al., *To Thine Own Self Be True? Incentive Problems in Personalized Law*, 62 WM. & MARY L. REV. 723 (2021).

¹¹⁷ E.g. Eldad Yechiam, *Behavioral Economics Enhancers*, 19 JUDGMENT & DECISION MAKING 1 (2024).

¹¹⁸ See generally Ninareh Mehrabi et al., *A Survey on Bias and Fairness in Machine Learning*, 54 ACM COMPUTING SURV. 1 (2021). See also Andreas Fuster et al., *Predictably Unequal? The Effects of Machine Learning on Credit Markets*, 77 J. FIN. 5 (2022) for evidence from the credit market that demonstrates that algorithmic decision-making, even when formally race-neutral, can produce systematically unequal outcomes for historically disadvantaged groups, thereby raising profound concerns about fairness and institutional legitimacy in automated regulatory systems.

¹¹⁹ AYRES & BRAITHWAITE, *supra* note 9.

¹²⁰ See Xukang Wang et al., *Beyond Surveillance: Privacy, Ethics, and Regulations in Face Recognition Technology*, 7 FRONTIERS IN BIG DATA 1 (2024) (surveying municipal bans on facial recognition in San Francisco and Somerville, Massachusetts, and examining proposed federal legislation prohibiting governmental and commercial use of the technology without warrants or consent).

systems that target discrete identifiers, behavioral recognition technologies are data-agnostic, aggregating any available information to enhance predictive accuracy regardless of its apparent nexus to the regulatory purpose. This raises privacy concerns extending beyond biometric capture. Optimizing accuracy incentivizes collection of data including personal habits, private communications, and health records, which are ordinarily protected under the right to informational privacy—a right recognized in U.S. constitutional law.¹²¹ Regulatory efficacy must therefore be balanced against informational privacy, a tension that intensifies as predictive systems extract value from increasingly intimate behavioral data.¹²²

Additionally, the age of data has introduced a new kind of concern often captured within the privacy paradigm: the inclusion of personal—not necessarily formally private—information in publicly used databases. Here, the concern is with the exploitation of the self, as embodied in data, in the furtherance of public interests. In the market sphere, for example, companies’ use of aggregated individual data for profit generation is the target of intense critique and attempted subversion under the notion of “predictive privacy.”¹²³ In the regulatory context, agencies are expected to collect data on subjects’ compliance and use it in their rational decision-making process. Should progress in data collection and analysis capabilities entail a limitation on their public use?

Finally, exploiting cross-domain data on trustworthiness, which can be highly conducive to regulatory accuracy, may infringe upon people’s expectations of the degrees of privacy awarded to different spheres of human behavior. To the extent many individuals intuitively feel that their behavior in certain aspects of their lives and relationships (e.g., work, family, leisure) is separate and distinct,¹²⁴ taking all of them into similar account in the operation of a BRT algorithm may be understood as a violation of privacy.¹²⁵ The Obama administration’s 2012 Consumer Privacy Bill of Rights captured this idea—albeit in the context of market providers—in its insistence on

¹²¹ See Carmel Shachar & Carleen Zubrzycki, *Informational Privacy after Dobbs*, 75 ALA. L. REV. 1, 19–20 (2023) (explaining how the opinion of the Supreme Court in the *Dobbs* decision, which curtailed decisional privacy in the context of abortion, explicitly distinguished that claim from the “right to shield information from disclosure”). See *Dobbs v. Jackson Women's Health Organization*, 597 U.S. 215, 219 (2022). Cf. Mikayla Domingo, *One Nation, under Dobbs: How Dobbs v. Jackson Women’s Health Impacts Data Privacy for All*, 15 UC L. SCI. & TECH. J. 35, 37 (2024) (arguing that “*Dobbs* has the capacity to deteriorate the progress made in data privacy protections for everyone”).

¹²² See Tânia Carvalho et al., *Towards a Data Privacy-Predictive Performance Trade-Off*, 223 EXPERT SYS. WITH APPLICATIONS 119785 (2023) (reporting “evidence of a tradeoff between the ability of re-identification and predictive performance”).

¹²³ See Mühlhof, *supra* note 11; Rainer Mühlhoff, *Predictive Privacy: Collective Data Protection in the Context of Artificial Intelligence and Big Data*, BIG DATA & SOC’Y 1 (2023).

¹²⁴ See ELIZABETH ANDERSON, VALUE IN ETHICS AND ECONOMICS 1–16 (1993) (providing a foundational framing of the pluralist understanding of human experience).

¹²⁵ See Jonathan Schonscheck, *Privacy and Discrete “Social Spheres,”* 7 ETHICS & BEHAV. 221, 228 (1997) (“Modern life—especially economic and medical—requires the disclosure of information—some of it quite intimate—in particular social spheres. My right to privacy is violated when information is taken from one of these discrete spheres and made available in another—when information is trans-sphered, without my knowledge or consent.”).

“respect for context,” calling for companies to “collect, use, and disclose personal data in ways that are consistent with the context in which consumers provide the data.”¹²⁶

Still, these claims must be considered in an informed way by democratic societies. As one of us has shown elsewhere, privacy concerns are too often raised without enough empirical evidence about the costs of not collecting data to correct for past and ongoing information disparities.¹²⁷ Moreover, privacy claims have also been used as a proxy for corporate secrecy to hide corruption.¹²⁸

2. Equality

Data-driven BRTs can support efforts to enhance equal treatment in regulation. They can diminish the effects of unfounded stereotypes, preconceptions, and prejudices that underlie both explicit and implicit biases in human decision-making in general and in trust determinations in particular.¹²⁹ AI-driven systems can evaluate individuals independently from perceived group attachments, treating each person according to their own behavioral record rather than demographic proxies. Personalization through individual-specific data can thus mitigate prejudice and reduce discrimination by extending trust to members of historically disadvantaged groups based on their actual conduct. Moreover, by reducing the costs of enforcement and auditing, such technologies enable broader application of trust-based approaches across all constituencies—not only those traditionally at the front of the line.

Yet, like any predictive regulatory technology, data-driven BRTs, if deployed unchecked, also face the risk of reaffirming, perpetuating, amplifying, and entrenching prejudices and discriminatory practices.¹³⁰ As suggested above, facial recognition has long served as the poster child for AI bias, the cautionary tale dominating public discourse about algorithmic discrimination. But the phenomenon extends across the full range of predictive technologies now being deployed in regulatory contexts. An algorithm that arrives at regulatory trust assessments that systematically burden members of certain groups over others may reaffirm discriminatory practices because it

¹²⁶ *President Obama’s Privacy Bill of Rights: Encouraging a Collaborative Process for Digital Privacy Reform*, BERKELEY TECH. L.J. (Mar. 12, 2012), <https://btlj.org/2012/03/president-obamas-privacy-bill-of-rights-encouraging-a-collaborative-process-for-digital-privacy-reform/>. See Helen Nissenbaum, *Respecting Context to Protect Privacy: Why Meaning Matters*, 24 SCI. & ENG’G ETHICS 831 (2018).

¹²⁷ ORLY LOBEL, *THE EQUALITY MACHINE: HARNESSING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY FOR A BRIGHTER, MORE INCLUSIVE FUTURE* (2022).

¹²⁸ Orly Lobel, *The Problem With Too Much Data Privacy*, TIME MAG. (Oct. 27, 2022, 06:30 AM), <https://time.com/6224484/data-privacy-problem/>.

¹²⁹ See LOBEL, *supra* note 127.

¹³⁰ See Pauline T. Kim, *Manipulating Opportunity*, 106 VA. L. REV. 867, 871 (2020) (“[W]hen predictive algorithms are used to allocate access to opportunities, there is a significant risk that they will do so in a way that reproduces existing patterns of inequality and disadvantage”).

does not account for prior injustices that could have reduced a group’s compliance capital¹³¹ and led its members to mark lower on trustworthiness scores.

Race-based concerns have been strongly debated in the context of policy. For example, “if drug arrests in a community have previously skewed towards a particular racial group, then a prediction of future drug crimes based on that data will also skew towards that community.”¹³² It follows that “biased data can generate biased predictions.”¹³³ Even if an algorithm states that there is no factor relying on race, there is a fear that, because the factors of the algorithms are confidential, race as a factor may be incorporated through correlated variables.¹³⁴

In addition, as studies on overconfidence in automated systems have indicated, the very fact that a trust assessment was arrived at by an algorithm rather than a human being might give it additional credence precisely because it is ostensibly not tainted by human bias.¹³⁵ This effect risks crowding out important mental checks on bias and prejudice, especially compared to decision-making processes designed to curb the impact of bias.

In the context of human decision-making, an often-proposed solution to implicit biases in predictive screening is “blinding”—hiding bias-triggering pieces of information like race, gender, or age from the decision-maker.¹³⁶ This, however, is not likely to be effective in an automated context. The very capacity of algorithmic tools to arrive at relevant generalizations—even without directly taking into account “suspicious” data points such as race, gender, or income—means that blinding mechanisms are not likely to work and are in fact more likely to diminish accuracy without improving equality.¹³⁷

3. Autonomy

From a liberal perspective, BRTs must include a commitment to choice and agency. The legitimacy of holding people accountable to their pledges and past behaviors is based on the

¹³¹ See, e.g., Ola Ali-Saleh & Samira Obeid, *Compliance with COVID-19 Preventive Guidelines Among Minority Communities: The Case of Israeli Arabs*, 10 J. RACIAL & ETHNIC HEALTH DISPARITIES 1576, 1577 (2023) (explaining that “ethnic minorities tend to have lower levels of trust in governments and health authorities, leading to lower compliance with COVID-19 guidelines”).

¹³² Bakke, *supra* note 24, at 140.

¹³³ *Id.*

¹³⁴ LOBEL, *supra* note 127; see also Ralph Hertwig et al., *Blinding to Circumvent Human Biases: Deliberate Ignorance in Humans, Institutions, and Machines*, 19 PERSPECTIVES ON PSYCH. SCI. 849, 853 (2023) (“Merely removing biasing information and then letting algorithms learn is not enough to prevent bias and ensure fairness. Rather, human expertise and values must be explicitly incorporated throughout the entire design process”).

¹³⁵ See Raja Parasuraman & Dietrich H Manzey, *Complacency and Bias in Human Use of Automation: An Attentional Integration*, 52 HUM. FACTORS: J. HUM. FACTORS & ERGONOMICS SOC’Y 381, 381–410 (2010).

¹³⁶ Tamar Kricheli-Katz & Tali Regev, *How Many Cents on the Dollar? Women and Men in Product Markets*, 2 SCI. ADVANCES 1 (2016).

¹³⁷ Talia B. Gilles & Jann L. Spiess, *Big Data and Discrimination*, 86 U. CHI. L. REV. 459, 459–88 (2019).

assumption that people are free to decide how to act and are capable of making reasoned choices between significant alternatives, including when they are expected to act upon previous commitments. BRTs, which often operate by relieving trustworthy regulatees from auditing burdens based on their prior statements, are thus strongly tied to autonomy.

This means, however, that the design of data-driven BRTs must ensure that the regulatory tools do not impose a burden on subjects that limits choice or coerces behavior beyond what is required to fulfill the targeted public interest. BRT, especially when it relies on cross-domain evidence, could strongly incentivize or disincentivize various forms of behavior, sometimes with no relation to the specific purpose of the regulatory effort. Thus, a finding that ties behavior XX to higher risk of YY with sufficient statistical validity¹³⁸ leads to a lower trust assessment in the context of YY for those engaged in behavior XX. To maintain high trust scores in YY, people may be incentivized to alter their behavior XX, even if the behavior itself is not illegal or unethical and there is no obvious connection between the domains that can be rationally drawn.

Consider, for example, a study by Hino, Benami, and Brooks, which demonstrated that machine learning algorithms could predict environmental violations using both direct compliance indicators (such as past violations and inspection history) and seemingly unrelated factors (like facility location, population density, and proximity to other regulated entities).¹³⁹ While this predictive approach proved highly effective at identifying violations, it raises concerns about potential incentives for strategic behavior, as facilities might alter superficial characteristics or manipulate reported data to reduce their predicted risk scores and avoid regulatory scrutiny.

The incentive to limit distrust-triggering activities risks a chilling effect on free speech. Behaviors in the public sphere, like social media participation, are amenable to simple tracking and documenting. People may therefore be wary of openly expressing views and opinions or sharing experiences for the risk that their speech would be recorded and later used in assigning them trustworthiness levels in diverse life junctures like job interviews, applications for permits, or self-regulatory pledges.¹⁴⁰ Note that the protection of speech is especially crucial to ensure the freedom to voice minority and fringe perspectives, express views that are critical of the powers that be, and imagine alternatives to existing political, economic, and social orders. Indeed,

¹³⁸ See, e.g., Barbara C. Leigh, *Alcohol and Condom Use: A Meta-Analysis of Event-Level Studies*, 29 *SEXUALLY TRANSMITTED DISEASES* 476 (2002) (describing a study that demonstrates that, in some circumstances, alcohol use (a risky behavior) significantly predicts the likelihood of engaging in unprotected sex (another risky behavior). The effect sizes, represented by odds ratios (OR), show that individuals who consume alcohol are about 1.29 times more likely to engage in unprotected sex compared to when they do not consume alcohol. The effect is particularly pronounced for new sexual partners (OR = 1.62), suggesting that alcohol use may have a stronger influence on risky sexual behavior in less familiar or more novel sexual situations).

¹³⁹ See Hino et al., *supra* note 115.

¹⁴⁰ See Moritz Büchi et al., *The Chilling Effects of Digital Dataveillance: A Theoretical Model and an Empirical Research Agenda*, 9 *BIG DATA & SOCIETY* 1 (2022) (describing the chilling effect engendered by “People’s Sense of Dataveillance”).

noncompliance itself may be a useful means of providing authorities with “constructive criticism about the fit between policies and local conditions,”¹⁴¹ inducing and legitimating policy change. In many contexts, however, such opposition views are likely to factor negatively in trustworthiness assessments and hence be inhibited by BRTs. Indeed, data-driven BRTs could also construct trust profiles based on online behavior shy of outright expression (such as websites visited or followed), extending the concern beyond that of inhibited speech to the liberty to consume and consider the ideas, expressions, and products of others.¹⁴²

Beyond the possibility of creating skewed incentives for behavior in adjacent domains, BRTs which assign people with trustworthiness scores also risk creating “lock-in effects” that may entrench trust perceptions over time and thus limit people’s correction capacity.¹⁴³ Even if trust determinations are correct at the time of evaluation, people change, as do corporate cultures. If the technology is too static—failing to update trustworthiness assessments and account for character and condition development—it may discount and disincentivize the human capacity to evolve and improve.

Finally, any predictive regulatory technology relies to some extent on the known behavior of others. For algorithms to accurately predict individual behavior, they require information on the comparative behavior of many other individuals. In this sense, personalization only goes so far: BRTs can assign individual trust only by measuring personal information against statistical data. This fact invokes the concern of assigning accountability without responsibility, coming in tension with the autonomy-based premise of legal liability. While in other contexts of the law—namely criminal culpability—accountability is strongly tied to individual responsibility,¹⁴⁴ predictive regulatory technologies normally impose burdens on individuals due to the behavior of similarly

¹⁴¹ Lily L. Tsai, *Constructive Noncompliance*, 47 COMPAR. POL. 253, 253 (2015).

¹⁴² See Büchi et al., *supra* note 140. A study conducted in Russia found that individuals who expressed opposition to the government were perceived as less trustworthy. See Timothy Frye & Ekaterina Borisova, *Elections, Protest, and Trust in Government: A Natural Experiment from Russia*, 81 J. OF POL. 820 (2019). In a study from the United States, it was found that expressing opposing political views can lead to social discrimination and reduced trust, although the effect sizes were smaller than those observed in the study above (which came from an authoritarian regime). See Shanto Iyengar & Sean J. Westwood, *Fear and Loathing Across Party Lines: New Evidence on Group Polarization*, 59 AM. J. POL. SCI. 690 (2015).

¹⁴³ See Mireille Hildebrandt, *Code-Driven Law: Freezing the Future and Scaling the Past*, in IS LAW COMPUTABLE?: CRITICAL PERSPECTIVES ON LAW AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE 67, 78 (Simon Deakin & Christopher Markou eds., 2020) (“[C]ode-driven normativity scales the past; it is based on insights from past decisions and cannot reach beyond them. [...] code-driven normativity freezes the future; it cannot adapt to unforeseen circumstances due to the disambiguation that is inherent in code. Instead it can accommodate a range of additional rules that apply under alternative conditions, implying complex decision trees that hope to map future occurrences. This mapping is by definition underdetermined, not because of a lack of knowledge but due to the radical uncertainty that is the future”).

¹⁴⁴ See, e.g., Nicola Lacey & Hanna Pickard, *To Blame or to Forgive? Reconciling Punishment and Forgiveness in Criminal Justice*, 35 OXFORD J. LEGAL STUD. 665, 666 (2015) (describing the dominant focus of contemporary penal philosophy on blameworthiness, which “demands that the offender have the capacity for responsible agency: minimally, cognitive and volitional capacities such that they knew what they were doing when they committed the offence, and exercised choice and a sufficient degree of control in doing so”).

situated others.¹⁴⁵ Importantly, automated trust determinations are meant to rid the regulatory process of the biases and prejudices that characterize human discretion about differential enforcement. Still, they draw on the grouping effect essential to statistical analysis.

B. Externalities: BRTs' Spillover Effects

Governments are tasked with promoting public interest while avoiding undue violations of individual rights. The discussion thus far has been premised on the assumed public value of data-driven behavioral recognition technologies, focusing primarily on their impact on rights. Yet such technologies may also generate social effects that extend beyond the immediate purposes of regulation, effects that ought to be considered in evaluating the justifiability of their deployment. Some of these externalities may prove socially beneficial—others, detrimental. Costly externalities arise when individuals, groups, or society as a whole bear burdens from the use of behavioral recognition technologies without corresponding compensation. The challenge for legal design is therefore to create effective BRTs that not only respect rights and liberties but also account for BRTs' spillover effects.

The most common social externality concern with BRT is its potential effect on social cohesion and solidarity. The new frontier of BRT invokes fear of a “surveillance society”: a panoptical social condition of constant tracking, in which any act, choice, or expression—in both the physical and the virtual spheres—counts toward a person's trustworthiness score. Infused by dystopian imaginaries such as Orwell's *1984*, actual experiences with surveillance ecosystems such as the East German Stasi, and recent reports of the abuses of China's sprawling social credit system,¹⁴⁶ this is a vision of a society wrought by suspicion and doubt as it seeks to discriminate between those whom it perceives as “trustworthy” and those it does not. BRT may also harm the shared sense of collective engagement—political solidarity—often seen as necessary to sustain a thriving republican democracy.

Economist Jean Tirole's seminal analysis demonstrates the potentially corrosive effects of social scoring technologies on social cohesion. These systems aggregate diverse behavioral and attitudinal factors into composite trustworthiness assessments. Tirole's analysis reveals a troubling paradox: Such algorithmic systems function most effectively where organic social ties are weak, because strong interpersonal relationships generate contextual information that can counterbalance

¹⁴⁵ See Solon Barocas & Andrew D. Selbst, *Big Data's Disparate Impact*, 104 CAL. L. REV. 671, 677 (2016) (“[T]he very point of mining is to provide a rational basis upon which to distinguish between individuals and to reliably confer to the individual the qualities possessed by those who seem statistically similar”); Jessica M. Eaglin, *Constructing Recidivism Risk*, 67 EMORY L.J. 59, 85 (2017).

¹⁴⁶ See, e.g., MINXIN PEI, *THE SENTINEL STATE: SURVEILLANCE AND THE SURVIVAL OF DICTATORSHIP IN CHINA* 1 (2024).

mechanical trust assessments. More concerning, to the extent that these technologies assign trustworthiness by association and evaluate individuals according to the characteristics of their social networks, they create incentives to sever ties with low-scoring or divergent individuals because maintaining relationships with those deemed algorithmically untrustworthy threatens to lower one’s own score. The rational response is social sorting: clustering with similarly trustworthy individuals while distancing oneself from those who might taint one’s algorithmic reputation, ultimately fragmenting communities and undermining the social fabric.¹⁴⁷

The reverse side of the surveillance society concern imagines a “trust society”—a community that, through the diffusion of BRTs, learns to develop and maintain relationships based on trust and an expectation of compliance rather than on the risk of violation, breach, or betrayal.¹⁴⁸ Indeed, as we noted above, some empirical evidence exists in support of the thesis that more trust in regulatory and capital markets may improve both their legitimacy and performance. In this scenario, the improved capacity of data-driven BRTs to deploy trust in diverse regulatory contexts would make it more familiar and attractive, ushering in a new era of trust-based relationships between individuals and the regulatory state. Social welfare in the trust society is cast as a common cause, pursued in partnership between individual, market, and state actors.

In this era, when data and AI already pervade practically every market and regulatory sector, a balance between “Big Brother” fears and “trust society” hopes is attainable. The challenge is to design BRTs that avoid the paralyzing effect of Chinese-style social scoring regimes while maximizing the redeeming value of an ecosystem in which individuals, market actors, and regulators contribute jointly to an evolving dynamic of justified trust.

Beyond its effects on social cohesion, BRTs may induce wasteful investment in evasion by sophisticated subjects.¹⁴⁹ Not all data points that factor into a BRT’s assessment are mutable, and the algorithmic framework of regulation is often too complex—and sometimes proprietarily inaccessible—to enable successful evasion.¹⁵⁰ Nevertheless, BRT is likely to incentivize some investment in manipulation that would affect regulatory efficacy, for example if subjects attempt

¹⁴⁷ Jean Tirole, *Digital Dystopia*, 111 AM. ECON. REV. 2007 (2021). See also Kees van Kersbergen & Gert Tinggaard Svendsen, *Social Trust and Public Digitalization*, 39 AI & SOC’Y 1201, 1208–09 (2024) (pointing to the capacity of efficient AI-powered security measures to “also have an overlooked and non-desirable crowding-out effect on social trust”); PEI, *supra* note 146, at 10–11 (“Besides prevention, effective [governmental] surveillance produces spillover effects that further impede collective action on the part of the opposition. One of the key spillover effects is to induce in opponents a sense of fear and distrust”).

¹⁴⁸ This is how the Chinese social credit system envisions itself: Chun Peng, *Building a High-Trust Society: Lineage, Logic, and Limitations of China’s Social Credit System*, 24 CHINA REV. 107 (2024). See also Fredrika Björklund, *Trust and Surveillance: An Odd Couple or a Perfect Pair?*, in TRUST AND TRANSPARENCY IN AN AGE OF SURVEILLANCE 183–200 (Lora Anne Viola & Paweł Laidler eds., 2022) (exploring explanations for survey findings that indicate a “positive correspondence between trust in public institutions and acceptance of surveillance”).

¹⁴⁹ Barry et al., *supra* note 116.

¹⁵⁰ Porat & Strahilevitz, *supra* note 113, at 1454–56.

to mask or hide behaviors that are known to affect trust scores.¹⁵¹ The cross-domain nature of the technology also means that manipulators may try to offset “trust losses” in one area by pushing “trust gains” in another: Consider, for example, corporate use of ESG investments as a way to allay regulatory distrust in other aspects of the business endeavor.¹⁵²

Concerns with manipulation are often met by suggestions to reduce transparency to make tracking and gaming more costly and less likely to succeed.¹⁵³ In the context of public use of BRTs, however, transparency is both a fundamental democratic value to ensure governmental accountability and a central feature in a trust ecosystem, in which trust is sought not merely by regulatory subjects but by the regulatory apparatus itself. This is a reflection of the familiar tension between transparency and efficacy, a challenge faced by law enforcement organizations in the era of big data.¹⁵⁴

IV. A NORMATIVE ROADMAP FOR BRT LAW

A. *The Thin Legal Landscape*

Despite the growing integration of AI into public and private governance, there remains a conspicuous lack of concrete legal guidance on how to regulate AI systems in ways that genuinely safeguard democratic values, particularly when applied by government agencies to predict behavior. Much of the existing policy framework consists of high-level, aspirational declarations—such as executive orders and ethical guidelines—that exhort developers and agencies to “avoid harm” or “ensure fairness,”¹⁵⁵ but fall short of providing enforceable standards or actionable design principles.¹⁵⁶ These documents often emphasize abstract values such as transparency, accountability, and non-discrimination without creating mechanisms for implementation, monitoring, or redress.¹⁵⁷

¹⁵¹ See Cameron Anderson & Aiwa Shirako, *Are Individuals' Reputations Related to Their History of Behavior?* 94 J. PERSONALITY & SOC. PSYCH. 320 (2008) (describing three studies that found a correlation between reputation and previous behavior was relatively weak). However, this correlation was more pronounced for well-known individuals who garnered more social attention within the group. *Id.* In contrast, the actions of lesser known individuals had minimal impact on their reputation. *Id.*

¹⁵² Jonathan R. Macey, *ESG Investing: Why Here? Why Now?* 19 BERKELEY BUS. L.J. 258 (2022).

¹⁵³ For a detailed account—and a critical assessment—of this position, see Ignacio N. Cofone & Katherine J. Strandburg, *Strategic Games and Algorithmic Secrecy*, 64 MCGILL L.J. 623 (2019).

¹⁵⁴ See Lyria Bennett Moses & Louis de Koker, *Open Secrets: Balancing Operational Secrecy and Transparency in the Collection and Use of Data by National Security and Law Enforcement Agencies*, 41 MELB. U. L. REV. 530 (2017).

¹⁵⁵ See, e.g., SEAN MUSCH ET AL., CODIFYING ETHICS GUIDELINES FOR TRUSTWORTHY AI 13 (2025).

¹⁵⁶ Lobel, *supra* note 37, at 1075–1078.

¹⁵⁷ See, e.g., Matthew Cole et al., *Politics by Automatic Means? A Critique of Artificial Intelligence Ethics at Work*, 5 FRONT. IN A.I. 1, 9 (2022) (arguing that “if the jump from ethical theory to practice is to be successfully made, then

This normative vagueness is particularly problematic for trust-based regulation, which depends on institutional legitimacy and voluntary compliance rather than deterrence alone. Such frameworks require clarity in trustworthiness criteria, procedural justice in how assessments are made and contested, and reciprocal accountability between regulator and regulated.¹⁵⁸ Procedural justice fosters compliance by ensuring that individuals perceive decision-making as fair and consistent. Reciprocal accountability ensures that if the state demands trustworthiness from regulated parties, it is answerable for how it evaluates that trust. Current legal frameworks lack a robust body of automation rights articulating the entitlements of individuals subject to algorithmic decision-making: rights to contest adverse determinations, understand the basis for assessments, and opt out of automated processes.

This stands in contrast with FRT and biometrics use, which has prompted a series of proposals, regulations, and reports, advancing unevenly but visibly, driven largely by state law reforms and selective federal agency action. States such as Illinois, California, Texas, and Washington have enacted or expanded laws that directly regulate *physical and biological identifiers*—fingerprints, facial geometry, iris scans, and voiceprints.¹⁵⁹ Illinois’s Biometric Information Privacy Act (BIPA) has generated billions of dollars in settlements for improper biometric collection without consent.¹⁶⁰ BIPA requires private entities to secure written, informed consent before collecting or using biometric identifiers and imposes specific retention and destruction obligations.¹⁶¹ The California Privacy Rights Act (CPRA) treats biometric data as “sensitive personal information,” limiting its use and retention,¹⁶² while local bans and state

the field of AI ethics must progressively replace the dominant pattern of seeking consensus through increased abstraction with negotiating multistakeholder agreements through progressively greater levels of detail”); Brandon Richardson & Juan E. Gilbert, *A Framework for Fairness: A Systematic Review of Existing Fair AI Solutions*, J. A.I. RSCH 1, 2 (2021) (citing “[r]ecent research [that] suggests a disconnect between the fairness AI researchers creating these tools and the ML practitioners who are meant to apply them”).

¹⁵⁸ See, e.g., Robert Baldwin & Julia Black, *Really Responsive Regulation*, 71 MOD. L. REV. 59, 81 (2008) (“The really responsive regulatory body will not only lay the foundations for its detection and other work by establishing clarity on objectives, it will be clear regarding the regulatory logic that it will apply.”).

¹⁵⁹ Ariana Naranjo, *U.S. Biometric Data Laws*, TCW GLOBAL (Apr. 1, 2025), <https://www.tcwglobal.com/blog/u.s.-biometric-data-law#Virginia-Consumer-Data-Protection-Act>.

¹⁶⁰ See, e.g., Patrick McKnight, *Historic Biometric Privacy Suit Settles for \$650 Million*, A.B.A. (Jan. 28, 2021), https://www.americanbar.org/groups/business_law/resources/business-law-today/2021-february/historic-biometric-privacy-settlement/ (reporting that Facebook paid a \$650 million settlement under BIPA after their “Tag Suggestion” photo-labeling service complied enough data for the company to automatically recognize the faces of its users).

¹⁶¹ Biometric Information Privacy Act, 740 ILL. COMP. STAT. 14/15 (2008).

¹⁶² See California Consumer Privacy Act of 2018, CAL. CIV. CODE § 1798.140(ae) (West 2026). CPRA was approved by California voters through a ballot initiative known as Proposition 24, which expanded and amended the California Consumer Privacy Act of 2018. See Cameron F. Kerry & Caitlin Chin-Rothmann, *By Passing Proposition 24, California Voters Up the Ante on Federal Privacy Law*, BROOKINGS (Nov. 17, 2020), <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/by-passing-proposition-24-california-voters-up-the-ante-on-federal-privacy-law/>.

statutes restrict law enforcement’s use of real-time facial recognition.¹⁶³ Texas’s Capture or Use of Biometric Identifier Act and Washington’s biometric identifiers statute likewise mandate notice, consent, and security measures for facial geometry, fingerprints, and similar traits.¹⁶⁴ Bills in Congress such as the Facial Recognition and Biometric Technology Moratorium Act or the Commercial Facial Recognition Privacy Act would limit or temporarily ban facial recognition and other biometric surveillance by government or commercial actors.¹⁶⁵ Several cities, including San Francisco and Boston, prohibit municipal agencies from using facial recognition altogether, illustrating how physical biometrics have become a visible flashpoint for privacy reform.¹⁶⁶ At the federal level, the Federal Trade Commission (FTC) has asserted enforcement authority over biometric misuse as an unfair or deceptive practice, and federal agencies have issued guidance on biometric surveillance.¹⁶⁷ Other jurisdictions, including the UK and the European Union (EU), have also developed robust regulatory frameworks for FRT.¹⁶⁸

BRT, on the other hand, has garnered far less regulatory and policy attention. There is an urgent need to move beyond principles and toward a more operationalized framework for AI regulation—one that systematically integrates normative commitments and empirical insights concerning BRT deployment. Such a framework would not merely constrain harm after the fact but guide the design and deployment of AI systems *ex ante*, fostering trustworthiness through meaningful accountability mechanisms. The U.S. regulatory landscape is particularly lagging. While jurisdictions such as the EU have begun to codify enforceable obligations under instruments like the AI Act and the General Data Protection Regulation’s provisions on automated processing, American law remains underdeveloped.¹⁶⁹ The rapid developments of AI have governments racing to regulate these newfound capabilities that are affecting every aspect of modern-day society. The most comprehensive regulation to date is the EU’s AI Act, enacted in December 2023. The EU AI Act focuses on determining AI’s riskiest uses and technologies by companies and governments,

¹⁶³ See, e.g., Kate Conger, et al., *San Francisco Bans Facial Recognition Technology*, N.Y. TIMES (May 14, 2019), <https://www.nytimes.com/2019/05/14/us/facial-recognition-ban-san-francisco.html>.

¹⁶⁴ TEX. BUS. & COM. CODE ANN. § 5003.001 (West 2026); WASH. REV. CODE § 19.375.020 (2017).

¹⁶⁵ Facial Recognition and Biometric Technology Moratorium Act of 2023, S. 681, 118th Cong. (2023); Commercial Facial Recognition Privacy Act of 2019, S. 847, 116th Cong. (2019).

¹⁶⁶ S.F., CAL. ADMIN. CODE ch. 19B, § 19B.2 (2025); BOS., MASS. CODE OF ORDINANCES ch. 16, § 16-62 (2020).

¹⁶⁷ See U.S. Fed. Trade Comm’n, Policy Statement of the Federal Trade Commission on Biometric Information and Section 5 of the Federal Trade Commission Act (2023). For further analysis on the FTC’s policy statement on biometric information, see generally John Burroughs, *Twin Inadequacies in the FTC’s Recent Biometrics Policy Statement*, 3 UNIV. CHI. BUS. L. REV. 497 (2024).

¹⁶⁸ See, e.g., Denise Almeida et al., *The Ethics of Facial Recognition Technologies, Surveillance, and Accountability in an Age of Artificial Intelligence: A Comparative Analysis of US, EU, and UK Regulatory Frameworks*, 2 AI & ETHICS 377 (2022) (reviewing the FRTs’ regulatory frameworks in three jurisdictions and proposing a set of new regulatory methods for the protection of human rights).

¹⁶⁹ See John Hillman, *Smart Regulation: Lessons from the Artificial Intelligence Act*, 37 EMORY INT’L L. REV. 775, 781–82 (2023) (arguing that “[t]he United States should learn from the [EU AI Act] and seek to implement a federal regulatory system to protect its citizens and streamline innovation”).

including AI use in law enforcement, using biometrics such as facial recognition, deploying chatbots, and using software to create “deepfakes.”¹⁷⁰

On October 30, 2023, President Biden issued an executive order on the “Safe, Secure, and Trustworthy Development and Use of Artificial Intelligence” (EO), which provided a set of guidelines that executive agencies should follow to regulate AI. In contrast to the EU AI Act, the EO did not create binding legislation but instead provided a framework for regulatory agencies to manage the implications and risks associated with AI technologies while promoting their responsible innovation and application. The EO guided agencies to notify the federal government when training foundational models that pose serious risks to national security, economic security, or public health and safety. Additionally, the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) was tasked with developing rigorous standards for pre-testing and ensuring the safety of AI systems before public release. The EO called upon the Department of Commerce to develop standards for watermarking AI output.

Meanwhile, individual agencies have begun deploying AI for enforcement purposes without comprehensive governance frameworks. The IRS, for instance, announced a new enforcement initiative using artificial intelligence and advanced analytics to identify compliance risks among high-income taxpayers and complex partnerships.¹⁷¹ The Consumer Financial Protection Bureau (CFPB) attempted to establish a registry to track repeat corporate offenders, though this rule was subsequently rescinded.¹⁷² The Department of Justice (DOJ) has similarly emphasized leveraging data on corporate compliance history in enforcement decisions.¹⁷³

The Institute of Electrical and Electronic Engineers (IEEE)’s Global Initiative on Ethics of Autonomous and Intelligent Systems provides a set of ethical guidelines and standards for AI development. Additionally, in 2023, House and Senate committees held nearly three dozen hearings on AI and over thirty AI-focused bills were introduced in Congress. The Federal Trade Commission (FTC) is interacting with AI on the opposite side of the spectrum, prioritizing

¹⁷⁰ Lobel, *supra* note 12, at 864.

¹⁷¹ *IRS will use AI to help target partnerships and high net worth individuals*, RSM US LLP (Dec. 8, 2023), <https://rsmus.com/insights/services/business-tax/irs-use-ai-help-target-partnerships-high-net-worth-individuals.html>.

¹⁷² Consumer Fin. Prot. Bureau, Registry of Nonbank Covered Persons Subject to Certain Agency and Court Orders, 89 Fed. Reg. 56028 (July 8, 2024) (to be codified at 12 C.F.R. pt. 1092), *rescinded by* Registry of Nonbank Covered Persons Subject to Certain Agency and Court Orders; Rescission, 90 Fed. Reg. 48760 (Oct. 29, 2025); *see also* Rohit Chopra, *Prepared Remarks of CFPB Director Rohit Chopra on the Final Rule to Detect and Deter Repeat Offenders*, CONSUMER FIN. PROT. BUREAU (June 3, 2024), <https://www.consumerfinance.gov/about-us/newsroom/prepared-remarks-of-cfpb-director-rohit-chopra-on-the-final-rule-to-detect-and-deter-repeat-offenders/>.

¹⁷³ *Deputy Attorney General Lisa O. Monaco Delivers Remarks on Corporate Criminal Enforcement*, U.S. DEP’T OF JUST. (Sept. 15, 2022), <https://www.justice.gov/opa/speech/deputy-attorney-general-lisa-o-monaco-delivers-remarks-corporate-criminal-enforcement>.

investigation when AI is utilized.¹⁷⁴ The FTC authorized the use of a compulsory process in investigations into AI and generative AI products and services by incorporating the issuance of civil investigative demands (CIDs), similar to subpoenas.¹⁷⁵ In other cases, executive agencies have addressed AI outside of the EO, explaining that existing regulations apply to AI. For example, the Equal Employment Opportunity Commission (EEOC) and the FTC have stated that the same laws regarding discrimination and competition carry over to algorithmic decision-making. The CFPB asserted that legally required explanations regarding credit denial apply with the same force to decisions made by algorithms. Indeed, these three agencies, along with the DOJ, issued a joint statement in 2023 manifesting their commitment to using existing law to prevent bias and discrimination in AI, describing how AI falls within these agencies' civil rights enforcement authority.¹⁷⁶

These piecemeal developments underscore a broader pattern documented in comprehensive studies of federal agency AI adoption. While algorithmic tools are proliferating across regulatory functions, existing legal frameworks remain fragmented and largely nonbinding, lacking enforceable automation rights, operational design standards, or systematic guidance for trust-based regulatory applications.¹⁷⁷ These regulatory frameworks have yet to provide systemic and substantial principles for regulators in shifting to AI-based trust determinations. The following discussion aims to fill that void by suggesting the backbone for such an approach. Based on our previous analysis of the rights and interests impacted by the deployment of BRT, we identify four topics any principled regulatory use of such technologies must contend with: (1) careful use of past behavior information; (2) insistence on empirical accuracy and robustness; (3) assurance of sufficient transparency; and (4) openness to correction and reversal in view of data dynamism and regulatory failure.

B. Past Behavior: Ethical Behavioral Predictions

1. The Predictive Usefulness of Past Behavior and Personalization

In the absence of a well-developed doctrinal framework governing trust-based differentiation, the analysis necessarily turns to empirical and behavioral research, not as a substitute for law, but as a way of identifying the normative tradeoffs that any future legal framework must confront. One prominent empirical finding is that an individual's past behavior is often a strong predictor of future conduct. As we detailed above, reliance on past behavior also

¹⁷⁴ Olga V. Mack, *Legal Tech: The FTC's Enhanced Scrutiny on AI*, ACC DOCKET (Jan. 9, 2024), <https://docket.acc.com/legal-tech-ftcs-enhanced-scrutiny-ai>.

¹⁷⁵ *Id.*

¹⁷⁶ See Khan, *supra* note 110.

¹⁷⁷ See ENGSTROM ET AL., *supra* note 37; CARY COGLIANESE, A FRAMEWORK FOR GOVERNMENTAL USE OF MACHINE LEARNING 31 (Dec. 8, 2020) (report to the Admin. Conf. of the U.S.).

carries distinctive normative appeal because it focuses on the actual choices and actions of the person whose trustworthiness is being assessed, rather than on immutable traits such as race or gender or on structural conditions such as income or education. Unlike group-based predictors, which risk entrenching stigma¹⁷⁸ and imposing costs based on the behavior of others, behavior-based assessments can be understood as recognizing agency and responsibility for one's own decisions. At the same time, this approach raises a countervailing concern: that anchoring regulatory treatment to prior conduct may constrain an individual's ability to redefine themselves and to pursue new life paths unburdened by earlier mistakes. The central challenge for the design of BRTs is therefore not whether past behavior predicts future behavior, but how regulators can balance agency, equality, and the possibility of redemption.

Empirical research strongly supports the proposition that individuals who have previously transgressed are more likely to engage in future violations than those without such history. A meta-analysis of the research in the field found criminal history to be among the strongest predictors of recidivism, with a mean effect size (r) of 0.16.¹⁷⁹ More recent work from the Netherlands compared first-time offenders with repeat offenders and found that the latter exhibited a two-year recidivism rate of 47.2%, compared to 27.5% for those with no prior record.¹⁸⁰ The odds ratio for repeat offenders committing a new offense was 2.34 times that of first-time offenders.

This empirical reality provides one rationale for three-strikes laws. Beyond the moral culpability arguably exhibited in recurrent violations, repeated offenses serve as evidence of future risk that may justify incapacitation for public protection.¹⁸¹ In the personalized regulatory context, a parallel logic applies. The reliability of a person's pledge, and the state's capacity to extend trust and conserve enforcement resources accordingly, typically both incorporate information about prior regulatory violations. Put simply, regulators have good reason to inquire whether the subject was previously caught cheating.

Against this background, predictive machine-learning algorithms enable personalized regulatory treatment by tailoring enforcement intensity to the behavioral patterns of individual regulated entities. This personalization offers two principal advantages. First, it enhances regulatory accuracy by grounding predictions in individualized data rather than broad categorical

¹⁷⁸ See Linda S. Beres & Thomas D. Griffith, *Do Three Strikes Laws Make Sense? Habitual Offender Statutes and Criminal Incapacitation*, 87 GEO. L.J. 103, 117 (1998) ("It would be unfair to consider immutable characteristics such as race, sex, or national origin in determining sentence length, even if these factors were good predictors of recidivism").

¹⁷⁹ Gendreau et al., *supra* note 109, at 584.

¹⁸⁰ B.S.J. WARTNA ET AL., RECIDIVISM REPORT 2002-2008 (2011), <https://files01.core.ac.uk/download/pdf/56779669.pdf>.

¹⁸¹ See Beres & Griffith, *supra* note 178, at 113 (1998) ("Much of the appeal of Three Strikes statutes is grounded in the idea of the selective incapacitation of the most dangerous offenders").

assumptions.¹⁸² Second, it ensures that individuals are not penalized for the conduct of others, a concern that pervades group-based enforcement strategies.

Personalized prediction signals respect for individual autonomy by holding people accountable for their own prior choices. It also reduces the likelihood that BRTs will reinforce social disparities arising from compliance deficits among marginalized communities, whose members may face structural barriers to compliance unrelated to individual trustworthiness.¹⁸³ Yet personalization carries its own costs: the more granular the information collected for regulatory trust determinations, the more severe the technology's intrusion upon autonomy and privacy. Regulatory design must therefore calibrate the degree of personalization to balance predictive accuracy against these liberty interests.

2. Types of Behavior (Severity of Infractions)

Past behavior relevant to trust assessments varies considerably in its severity and antisocial character, raising complex normative and empirical questions about which infractions should inform algorithmic predictions. A BRT designed to predict illegal or unethical conduct will naturally look at the subject's prior record: Has she violated the law in question before (same-domain analysis), or other laws that bear some relationship to the regulated domain?

The empirical literature on criminal recidivism provides substantial support for same-domain predictions. As noted in the prior section, criminal history consistently emerges as a significant predictor across studies, though effect sizes remain modest by conventional statistical standards.¹⁸⁴ This finding has been replicated across diverse populations and jurisdictions. Studies comparing repeat and first-time offenders consistently demonstrate elevated recidivism rates among those with prior criminal involvement, with the magnitude varying by methodology and follow-up period.¹⁸⁵ This predictive value extends to specialized populations as well. Research on offenders with mental disorders confirms that criminal history retains validity even when controlling for mental health factors.¹⁸⁶ These findings establish criminal history as a consistently

¹⁸² Although accuracy may not always be optimized by personalization. See Lucas Monteiro Paes et al., *On the Epistemic Limits of Personalized Prediction*, NEURAL INFO. PROCESSING SYS. (2022).

¹⁸³ See David M. Konisky & Christopher Reenock, *Compliance Bias and Environmental (In)Justice*, 75 J. POL. 506, 507 (2013) (“[T]he costs associated with noncompliance (firms) and failure to detect noncompliance (bureaucrats) are lower in poor and minority communities because these communities have fewer resources with which to document and protest noncompliance”). See also Anat Gofen et al., *It Takes a Village to Build Illegality: Minorities' Noncompliance as Manifestation of Distrust*, 34 GOVERNANCE 983 (2020).

¹⁸⁴ See Gendreau et al., *supra* note 109, at 588.

¹⁸⁵ For a review of many longitudinal studies on recidivism patterns see generally NAT'L RSCH. COUNCIL, CRIMINAL CAREERS AND “CAREER CRIMINALS” (1st ed. 1986).

¹⁸⁶ See James Bonta et al., *The Prediction of Criminal and Violent Recidivism Among Mentally Disordered Offenders: A Meta-Analysis*, 123 PSYCH. BULL. 123 (1998) (conducting a meta-analysis demonstrating that criminal history variables are the strongest predictors of recidivism among mentally disordered offenders; finding that major predictors

useful predictor, though the generally modest effect sizes reflect the multifactorial nature of criminal behavior and the inherent challenges of predicting human conduct.

Beyond formal criminal records, should predictive algorithms incorporate information from social media reports about antisocial behavior, or ratings from peer-to-peer platforms such as Uber or Airbnb? And should it matter, in terms of rights infringement, whether such information was posted by the individual herself or by someone else?

Research on online behavioral indicators suggests such information may provide insights into trustworthiness, though predictive validity varies across contexts and platforms. Cabral and Hortaçsu's analysis of eBay's reputation system demonstrated that seller ratings meaningfully predicted future transaction outcomes, providing evidence that digital reputation mechanisms can capture genuine differences in reliability.¹⁸⁷ The predictive power of digital traces extends beyond commercial transactions. A study of social network behavior found that Facebook "likes" could predict personality traits with surprising accuracy, including conscientiousness—a trait correlated with rule-following behavior—though the authors cautioned about the privacy implications of such predictive capabilities.¹⁸⁸ While these findings suggest potential applications for assessing trustworthiness across digital platforms, scholars have noted significant limitations and risks. The aggregation of digital behavioral data for predictive purposes raises substantial privacy concerns and may create new forms of discrimination based on online activity patterns.¹⁸⁹ Moreover, the cross-platform validity of digital reputation measures remains an open empirical question, as different online environments may elicit different behavioral patterns from the same individual.

From a pure accuracy standpoint, "soft" (i.e., not criminal) infractions may sometimes prove more instructive than formally criminal ones. A longitudinal study that tracked subjects from childhood to adulthood found that early behavioral indicators, including school disciplinary actions and minor social infractions, predicted adult criminal behavior more accurately than later formal charges.¹⁹⁰ This suggests that soft behavioral data may capture underlying antisocial tendencies before they manifest in serious criminal activity.

of recidivism are largely shared with nondisordered offenders; and calculating effect sizes for 35 general and 27 violent recidivism predictors across 64 samples).

¹⁸⁷ Luís Cabral & Ali Hortaçsu, *The Dynamics of Seller Reputation: Evidence from eBay*, 58 J. INDUS. ECON. 54 (2010).

¹⁸⁸ Michal Kosinski et al., *Private Traits and Attributes Are Predictable from Digital Records of Human Behavior*, 110 PROC. NAT'L ACAD. SCI. 5802 (2013).

¹⁸⁹ Omer Tene & Jules Polonetsky, *Big Data for All: Privacy and User Control in the Age of Analytics*, 11 NW. J. TECH. & INTELL. PROP. 239 (2013).

¹⁹⁰ Terrie Moffitt et al., *Males on the Life-Course-Persistent and Adolescence-Limited Antisocial Pathways: Follow-Up at Age 26 Years*, 14 DEV. & PSYCHOPATHOLOGY 179 (2002).

Yet a rights-oriented perspective counsels caution. Incorporating ethical or social infractions into regulatory algorithms would intensify an already pervasive surveillance ecosystem in which constant ratings already affect access to diverse social and material opportunities. The government’s systematic exploitation of such information to calibrate differential enforcement levels adds a coercive dimension to the surveillance economy. If sufficiently accurate predictions can be achieved without this data (determining what counts as “sufficient” is the core balancing challenge), a strong argument exists for excluding such information from algorithmic design.

We acknowledge that data-driven technologies often operate under the assumption that “bigger is better,” in the sense that more data is always preferable to less data in predictive analytics.¹⁹¹ This logic would ordinarily push designers to include all available information, especially when AI systems operate through causal connections that resist intuitive explanation. However, different categories of past behavior evidence vary in their impact on rights, particularly through their nudging effects on choices in constitutionally protected domains. Algorithmic design should therefore seek to exploit information that minimizes rights infringement while achieving regulatory objectives. This demands a scaling analysis that weighs the importance of the public interest being advanced against the differential effects of incorporating various types of behavioral data.

3. Cross-Domain Information

Past behavior measures of trustworthiness normally deduce a prediction about future behavior from a similar behavior in the past, criminal recidivism being the typical example. But how similar should the predicted behavior be to the one that occurred in the past to warrant regulatory attention? Under different levels of predictive resolution, a driver caught speeding can be predicted to drive unsafely, to disrespect the law, to flout authority, and so forth. Past behavior can reveal different tendencies, with varying levels of accuracy and with varying degrees of rationally explainable relation between past and predicted behaviors. The more abstract the inference from behavior to prediction, the harder it becomes to justify in terms of responsibility and respect to one’s choices.

This challenge is compounded by the fact that past behavior in one domain can sometimes be a predictor of behavior in another, seemingly unrelated domain. The empirical literature presents a complex picture regarding the validity of cross-domain behavioral predictions, with significant implications for regulatory enforcement strategies. Gottfredson and Hirschi’s influential general theory of crime argues that low self-control manifests consistently across diverse rule-breaking behaviors, from criminal violations to regulatory infractions.¹⁹² This

¹⁹¹ See, e.g., Enric Junqué de Fortuny et al., *Predictive Modeling With Big Data: Is Bigger Really Better?*, 1 *BIG DATA* 215 (2013). See also VIKTOR MAYER-SCHÖNBERGER & KENNETH CUKIER, *BIG DATA: A REVOLUTION THAT WILL TRANSFORM HOW WE LIVE, WORK, AND THINK* (2013).

¹⁹² MICHAEL R. GOTTFREDSON & TRAVIS HIRSCHI, *A GENERAL THEORY OF CRIME* (1990).

theoretical framework has received substantial empirical support: A comprehensive meta-analysis found meaningful correlations between self-control deficits and various forms of deviant behavior, suggesting some degree of cross-domain consistency in rule violations.¹⁹³ Similarly, research in tax compliance has identified connections between different types of legal violations, with studies finding that individuals with certain regulatory infractions show elevated rates of tax noncompliance.¹⁹⁴ However, the predictive validity of cross-domain information remains contested. Life-course criminology research demonstrates that behavioral patterns can change substantially over time due to social bonds, life transitions, and situational factors, challenging assumptions about stable cross-domain consistency. These mixed findings suggest that while cross-domain behavioral information may possess some predictive value, regulatory agencies must carefully weigh its accuracy against the privacy and autonomy costs of comprehensive data integration, particularly given the modest effect sizes typically observed in behavioral prediction research.¹⁹⁵

One of the hallmark capabilities of predictive AI is pooling a multitude of seemingly random data points and revealing regularities, correlations, and trends, unnoticeable to the human mind, that can then be used to predict future events and behaviors. Accordingly, AI-powered BRTs might gain specially useful information from evidence on an individual's behavior in other spheres of life—what if speeding is correlated with tax cheating? Should the tax authorities, in calibrating their auditing efforts, be allowed to include in their calculus traffic ticket information?¹⁹⁶

The expansion of “data federalism”—the exchange or pooling of data among distinct governmental entities—is the institutional backbone of the regulatory capacity to consider past behavior across domains.¹⁹⁷ Existing legal discourse has examined data-sharing arrangements between public agencies as an issue of constitutional significance, impacting both jurisdictional delimitation and constitutional safeguards against undue attainment of evidence in the criminal process.¹⁹⁸ In the context of BRTs, data sharing may enhance the accuracy of predictive algorithms while restricting individuals' privacy and autonomy and exacerbating the weighing-down-by-the-past effect. At the same time, diversifying the sources of information for the predictive model makes it harder for subjects to strategically game it, improving its effectiveness and disincentivizing wasteful investment in avoidance.

¹⁹³ Travis C. Pratt & Francis T. Cullen, *The Empirical Status of Gottfredson and Hirschi's General Theory of Crime: A Meta-Analysis*, 38 CRIMINOLOGY 931 (2000).

¹⁹⁴ See, e.g., Daniel S. Nagin & Raymond Paternoster, *The Preventive Effects of the Perceived Risk of Arrest: Testing an Expanded Conception of Deterrence*, 29 CRIMINOLOGY 561 (1991) (examining relationships between different forms of legal compliance).

¹⁹⁵ ROBERT J. SAMPSON & JOHN H. LAUB, *CRIME IN THE MAKING: PATHWAYS AND TURNING POINTS THROUGH LIFE* (1995).

¹⁹⁶ Cf. Thomas M. Porcano, *Correlates of Tax Evasion*, 9 J. ECON. PSYCH. 47 (1988) (examining multiple variables that could affect tax evasion behavior, and finding, inter alia, that “most evaders appeared to be dishonest in other activities.” *Id.* at 64).

¹⁹⁷ Bridget A. Fahey, *Data Federalism*, 135 HARV. L. REV. 1007 (2022).

¹⁹⁸ *Id.*

BRT designers would normally seek as much available data as possible, and, in the governmental context, try to attain any cross-domain information collected by other agencies. To the extent that the amount and diversity of data included in the predictive analysis is correlated with severity of harm to privacy and autonomy (as it implies greater intrusion into more areas of individuals' choices), the challenge is to devise algorithms that exploit as little data as possible, or data that is culled from as few domains as possible, and still reach sufficient levels of efficacy to fulfill the BRT's purpose.

The balance here would require denoting domains of behavior according to their functional distance from the core behavior being regulated. As domains become rationally less related to the regulated behavior, the BRT design would need to show more compelling justification for its inclusion in the predictive analysis—namely, empirically substantiated evidence that the added information would significantly improve the algorithm's accuracy, compared to its exclusion.

C. Accuracy and Robustness Thresholds

The accuracy and robustness thresholds embedded within BRTs fundamentally determine both their regulatory effectiveness and their potential for raising—and allaying—constitutional concerns, creating complex normative trade-offs that demand careful institutional design.¹⁹⁹ We describe three methodological benchmarks that any reasoned trust-measurement tool must account for in its design in order to withstand normative review.

1. Statistical Sufficiency Standards

Under any level of constitutional scrutiny, rights-restricting regulatory policies must withstand some degree of factual robustness testing. In other words, the constitutional legitimacy of BRTs fundamentally depends on establishing rigorous standards for statistical sufficiency that can justify differential governmental treatment of similarly situated individuals. When regulatory agencies deploy algorithmic systems to predict compliance behavior, they must distinguish between mere statistical association and genuine predictive relationships that can support the exercise of governmental power to restrict rights.²⁰⁰ Thus, for example, regression analysis, which isolates the effect of specific behavioral predictors while controlling for confounding variables, provides a more robust foundation for regulatory decision-making than simple correlational analysis, which may conflate spurious associations with genuine causal relationships.²⁰¹ However, the legal significance of statistical relationships cannot be determined by mathematical measures

¹⁹⁹ See generally Kosinski et al., *supra* note 188 (demonstrating the predictive power of digital behavioral traces while noting privacy implications).

²⁰⁰ See generally Cass R. Sunstein, *The Arithmetic of Arsenic*, 90 GEO. L.J. 2255, 2265–70 (2001) (discussing standards of evidence required for regulatory decision-making).

²⁰¹ Cf. *Daubert v. Merrell Dow Pharms., Inc.*, 509 U.S. 579, 590–95 (1993) (establishing standards for evaluating the reliability of scientific evidence in legal proceedings).

alone; effect sizes must be evaluated against constitutional standards of proportionality and the severity of rights infringement they entail.²⁰²

The empirical literature on cross-domain behavioral prediction illustrates these challenges. While Gottfredson and Hirschi's general theory of crime posits that low self-control drives consistent rule-breaking across domains,²⁰³ subsequent meta-analytic research has found only moderate effect sizes supporting such cross-domain consistency.²⁰⁴ These modest correlations—typically in the range of $r = 0.28$ to 0.47 —raise fundamental questions about whether such predictive relationships are sufficiently robust to justify differential regulatory treatment, particularly given the potential for algorithmic systems to perpetuate existing patterns of discrimination.²⁰⁵ Agencies and courts must therefore develop frameworks for evaluating when predictive accuracy reaches a threshold sufficient to overcome constitutional presumptions against differential treatment, recognizing that statistical significance does not automatically translate into legal justification for disparate governmental action.²⁰⁶

The challenge lies in establishing empirically grounded yet constitutionally sensitive standards that can guide regulatory agencies in balancing predictive utility against fundamental rights. Our current knowledge about behavioral recognition technologies remains insufficient to determine whether their predictions are genuinely accurate. Prediction models cannot be easily validated against future observations; the mechanisms causing risk and their relation to predictor variables are neither constant nor well understood, and changing enforcement policies threaten long-term model validity. Moreover, these technologies risk generating self-fulfilling prophecies: When resources concentrate on flagged individuals, increased scrutiny produces more detected violations, reinforcing the algorithm's apparent accuracy even when predictions do not reflect underlying reality.²⁰⁷ These loops can cause models to grow increasingly confident in predictions that are artifacts of the intervention itself.²⁰⁸ Such epistemic limitations counsel incremental deployment with robust mechanisms for independent validation.

²⁰² See *Mathews v. Eldridge*, 424 U.S. 319, 335 (1976) (establishing framework for balancing governmental interests against individual rights in administrative proceedings).

²⁰³ GOTTFREDSON & HIRSCHI, *supra* note 192, at 85–92.

²⁰⁴ Pratt & Cullen, *supra* note 193, at 940–45.

²⁰⁵ Barocas & Selbst, *supra* note 145, at 692–99 (examining how seemingly neutral algorithmic systems can perpetuate discrimination).

²⁰⁶ See JACOB COHEN, *STATISTICAL POWER ANALYSIS FOR THE BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES* 79–81 (2d ed. 1988) (establishing benchmarks for interpreting effect sizes in behavioral research).

²⁰⁷ See Greg Ridgeway, *Linking Prediction and Prevention*, 12 *CRIMINOLOGY & PUB. POL'Y* 545, 547–48 (2013)

²⁰⁸ See Jeremias Adams-Prassl et al., *Directly Discriminatory Algorithms*, 86 *MOD. L. REV.* 144, 167–68 (2022); Danielle Ensign et al., *Runaway Feedback Loops in Predictive Policing*, 81 *PROC. OF MACH. LEARNING RSCH.* 1 (2018).

2. Dichotomous vs. Linear Measures

Algorithmic regulation faces a fundamental design choice between binary and continuous trust assessment systems. This choice reflects the broader legal tension between rules and standards, with profound implications for both administrative efficiency and constitutional rights protection.²⁰⁹ This choice becomes particularly consequential when agencies seek to base regulatory decisions on individuals' past behavior, as the method of classification directly affects both the accuracy of behavioral predictions and the degree of individualized treatment accorded to regulatory subjects.

Binary classification systems, where individuals are sorted into discrete categories of “trustworthy” or “untrustworthy” based on past behavior, offer the administrative advantages traditionally associated with bright-line rules.²¹⁰ Such systems provide clear decision-making criteria and reduce the cognitive burden on enforcement personnel, much like three-strikes laws that mandate specific consequences for repeat offenders regardless of individual circumstances.²¹¹ However, empirical analysis of binary approaches reveals significant constitutional and practical limitations. Research on three-strikes implementation has documented not only minimal deterrent effects but also substantial racial disparities that persist even after controlling for offense characteristics, suggesting that seemingly objective behavioral criteria can perpetuate systemic bias.²¹² The fundamental problem lies in binary systems' inability to capture the complex gradations of risk and trustworthiness that characterize real-world regulatory compliance, leading to arbitrary line-drawing that may violate substantive due process requirements.²¹³

Courts have increasingly recognized these constitutional vulnerabilities, particularly when binary systems rely on past behavioral indicators that serve as proxies for protected characteristics. The judicial treatment of stop-and-frisk policies illustrates these concerns: Despite being ostensibly based on objective behavioral factors, such programs have consistently failed to demonstrate statistical validity and have exhibited profound racial disparities.²¹⁴ More recently, courts examining algorithmic risk assessment tools have identified similar due process problems

²⁰⁹ Louis Kaplow, *Rules Versus Standards: An Economic Analysis*, 42 DUKE L.J. 557, 570–75 (1992); see also Cass R. Sunstein, *Problems with Rules*, 83 CAL. L. REV. 953, 959–65 (1995) (examining the trade-offs between rules and standards in regulatory contexts).

²¹⁰ See Antonin Scalia, *The Rule of Law as a Law of Rules*, 56 U. CHI. L. REV. 1175, 1178–80 (1989) (advocating for rule-based approaches to enhance predictability and reduce arbitrary enforcement).

²¹¹ See generally FRANKLIN E. ZIMRING ET AL., PUNISHMENT AND DEMOCRACY: THREE STRIKES AND YOU'RE OUT IN CALIFORNIA 3–20 (2001) (analyzing the implementation and effects of mandatory sentencing schemes).

²¹² See Daniel S. Kessler & Steven D. Levitt, *Using Sentence Enhancements to Distinguish Between Deterrence and Incapacitation*, 42 J. L. & ECON. 343, 350–55 (1999) (finding limited deterrent effects of three-strikes laws).

²¹³ Cf. *Mathews v. Eldridge*, 424 U.S. 319, 335 (1976) (establishing framework for evaluating procedural due process requirements that emphasizes individualized consideration).

²¹⁴ *Floyd v. City of New York*, 959 F. Supp. 2d 540, 562–75 (S.D.N.Y. 2013) (finding stop-and-frisk practices violated Fourth and Fourteenth Amendments due to lack of individualized suspicion and racial targeting); see also DAVID A. HARRIS, *PROFILES IN INJUSTICE: WHY RACIAL PROFILING CANNOT WORK* 80–95 (2002) (documenting the statistical and constitutional problems with profile-based enforcement).

with binary classification systems that reduce complex individual circumstances to simple categorical determinations.²¹⁵ These decisions suggest that regulatory agencies employing past behavior information must demonstrate not only that their classification schemes possess predictive validity, but also that they avoid the arbitrary distinctions that characterize constitutionally problematic bright-line approaches.

Continuous assessment systems, which place individuals along graduated scales of trustworthiness based on comprehensive analysis of past behavior, offer superior constitutional compliance by enabling truly individualized regulatory treatment.²¹⁶ Such systems can account for the severity, frequency, and context of past violations while remaining sensitive to individual circumstances that binary approaches necessarily ignore. Research on algorithmic fairness demonstrates that continuous scoring systems consistently outperform binary classification schemes both in predictive accuracy and in avoiding discriminatory outcomes.²¹⁷ However, the constitutional advantages of continuous systems come at substantial administrative cost, requiring sophisticated algorithmic infrastructure and extensive data processing capabilities that may exceed many agencies' institutional capacity.²¹⁸

The optimal approach likely involves graduated, multi-tiered systems that capture meaningful behavioral distinctions without imposing prohibitive resource demands. Such systems can stratify regulatory subjects into several risk categories based on empirically validated factors drawn from past behavior, enabling differentiated regulatory treatment while maintaining administrative feasibility.²¹⁹ The key lies in designing classification schemes granular enough to avoid the constitutional problems of crude binary distinctions while remaining simple enough to implement within existing regulatory frameworks. This middle path recognizes that perfect individualization may be neither practically achievable nor constitutionally required, provided that classification systems demonstrate empirical validity and avoid arbitrary line-drawing that fails to correspond to meaningful differences in regulatory risk.

²¹⁵ Julia Angwin et al., *Machine Bias*, in *ETHICS OF DATA AND ANALYTICS: CONCEPTS AND CASES* 254–264 (2022); see also Julia Angwin et al., *Machine Bias*, PROPUBLICA (May 23, 2016), <https://www.propublica.org/article/machine-bias-risk-assessments-in-criminal-sentencing> (documenting racial bias in COMPAS risk assessment algorithm used in criminal sentencing).

²¹⁶ See KENNETH CULP DAVIS, *DISCRETIONARY JUSTICE: A PRELIMINARY INQUIRY* 55–60 (1969) (arguing that individualized assessment is essential to fair administrative treatment).

²¹⁷ See Barocas & Selbst, *supra* note 145, at 695–705 (2016) (analyzing how algorithmic classification systems can achieve more nuanced and fair outcomes); see also Cynthia Dwork et al., *Fairness Through Awareness*, INFO. TECH. CONVERGENCE SERV. 214, 220–25 (2012).

²¹⁸ Cary Coglianese & David Lehr, *Regulating by Robot: Administrative Decision Making in the Machine-Learning Era*, 105 GEO. L.J. 1147, 1180–87 (2017) (analyzing institutional capacity constraints on agency adoption of sophisticated algorithmic systems).

²¹⁹ See BERNARD E. HARCOURT, *AGAINST PREDICTION: PROFILING, POLICING, AND PUNISHING IN AN ACTUARIAL AGE* 180–90 (2019) (advocating for more nuanced approaches to risk assessment that avoid crude binary classifications).

3. Universal vs. Differential Application

A related design choice involves the universality versus contextual sensitivity of trustworthiness metrics. Universal approaches assume that behavioral predictors operate consistently across diverse populations and cultural contexts, offering administrative efficiency but potentially overlooking important cultural and socioeconomic variations in regulatory compliance patterns.²²⁰ Conversely, culturally contingent systems that adjust trust assessments based on demographic or geographic factors may enhance predictive accuracy while raising serious constitutional concerns about differential treatment based on group membership.²²¹

Thus, some past behaviors that are perceived from one perspective as anti-social, and may even be illegal, could be norm-validating and trust-building when taken from another perspective. Consider, for example, a worker joining an illegal labor picket in solidarity with her colleagues, or a religious individual claiming an exemption from, or indeed disobeying, a legal mandate in conscientious commitment to her belief community's decrees. Is the explicit social deviation embedded in the behavior "set off" by its contextually trust-affirming nature? Questions of accuracy, tolerance, and choice are conjoined in weighing the legitimacy of the regulatory tool. Penalizing an individual for behavior that is perceived by her relevant normative community as conscientious may amount to a harm to freedoms of association, culture, or religious exercise. Further, it may fail to accurately account for individuals' complex and often context-specific relation to trustworthiness, commitment, and truthfulness.

Given these risks, the challenge for regulators is to devise sufficiently robust differentiations among members or groups in the regulated class. These differentiations should enable consideration of the varying degrees of antisociality reflected in similar actions taken in disparate conditions, while at the same time maintaining a commitment to equal treatment and avoiding incentives for free riding on community norms to elicit regulatory exemptions.

D. *Explainability-Transparency*

In a democratic society, especially one seeking to foster a trust-based regulatory ecosystem, it is essential for people to trust regulatory bodies. This challenge is compounded by the use of regulatory algorithms, as people tend to hold machine learning systems to a higher standard than human decision-making, reflecting a deeply ingrained fear of handing machines responsibility

²²⁰ GEERT HOFSTEDÉ, *CULTURE'S CONSEQUENCES: INTERNATIONAL DIFFERENCES IN WORK-RELATED VALUES* 25–30 (1980) (demonstrating substantial cross-cultural variation in behavioral norms and expectations).

²²¹ See Pauline T. Kim, *Data-Driven Discrimination at Work*, 58 WM. & MARY L. REV. 857, 890–95 (2017) (analyzing constitutional problems with employment algorithms that incorporate demographic factors).

over important roles.²²² Regulatory transparency about the use of AI and algorithmic explainability about the way the technology operates and arrives at its predictions are therefore central to garnering public trust in, and cooperation with, BRTs. This in turn bolsters their democratic legitimacy.²²³

However, most people do not have the necessary technical knowledge to understand the algorithms behind AI, and indeed some AI tools operate in a “black box” that is not fully decipherable even to their human developers. This invokes both practical and conceptual challenges: How can regulators gain the trust of a public when they are unable to fully and openly flesh out the processes that drive their enforcement choices? At the same time, just as algorithmic transparency and explainability enhance the legitimacy of data-based BRTs, they also harm privacy and proprietary interests, open up possibilities of manipulation by sophisticated regulatory subjects, and are less operational in large-scale applications.²²⁴ This can be described as an efficacy-legitimacy paradox. Regulators are required to use effective and narrowly tailored means that could rationally fulfill the regulatory purpose, sometimes justifying limiting transparency to fully utilize technological capacities; but they also have to be accountable and appear rational, demands that are bolstered by greater transparency. Balancing the different demands is a central challenge of a new regulatory system seeking legitimation.²²⁵

E. Reversibility

BRTs are likely to be less harmful to individual rights and public interests if their effects are reversible or avoidable. BRTs that are sensitive to the degree of mutability of the data points they process or that are themselves subject to review, updating, and correction are less likely to be as restrictive as BRTs that rely on fixed traits or that entrench distinctions, biases, and prejudices. We treat each of these two points in the following sections.

1. Immutability of Data Points

As already noted above, a common critique of screening and profiling technologies focuses on their reliance on practically immutable traits such as race, gender, ethnicity, or age. Differentiated enforcement based on such attributes is often taken as *prima facie* discrimination,

²²² See, e.g., Azim Shariff et al., *How Safe is Safe Enough? Psychological Mechanisms Underlying Extreme Safety Demands for Self-Driving Cars*, 126 *TRANSP. RSCH. PART C: EMERGING TECHS.*, art. 103069 (2021).

²²³ See Seth Lazar, *Legitimacy, Authority, and Democratic Duties of Explanation*, in *OXFORD STUDIES IN POLITICAL PHILOSOPHY VOL. 10* 28 (David Sobel & Steven Wall eds., 2024).

²²⁴ See Joshua A. Kroll et al., *Accountable Algorithms*, 165 *U. PA. L. REV.* 633, 657–60 (2017) (describing reasons to be wary of full algorithmic transparency).

²²⁵ See, e.g., Karl de Fine Licht & Jenny de Fine Licht, *Artificial Intelligence, Transparency, and Public Decision-Making: Why Explanations Are Key When Trying to Produce Perceived Legitimacy*, 35 *AI & SOC’Y* 917, 923–24 (2020) (suggesting that providing reasons for AI determinations can provide sufficient legitimacy to a regulatory system, while avoiding the costs of full algorithmic transparency).

since it affects people's access to various opportunities or endowments based on attributes they did not choose and cannot avoid. This also creates, validates, and entrenches prejudicial treatment of group members—the very opposite of an empirically-grounded regulatory program.

Accordingly, predictive algorithms can be evaluated by the weight they allot to immutable versus mutable attributes in the regulated subjects. Assuming different kinds of data can be used to reach similar levels of regulatory efficacy, a greater reliance on immutable data points would make the BRT more constitutionally suspect. In contrast, greater reliance on data points reflecting choice and control would indicate a better likelihood of justifiability.²²⁶

The complexity of this analysis lies, of course, in the definition of both “mutable” and “immutable” attributes. It is relatively easy to state that an algorithm fails the immutability test if it accounts heavily for a business owner's racial identity as a marker of trustworthiness in regulatory compliance assessments. But other markers which are less obviously immutable, such as names, addresses, and income levels, could be close proxies for that trait, effectively leading to similar levels of prejudice. This is why BRT designers are wary of crude blinding mechanisms, given that sophisticated algorithms can often readily “deduce” missing pieces of data from other bits of correlated information. Hence, the argument here is not for blinding BRTs, but rather accounting for the degree of reliance on immutable data points or their empirically proven proxies.

Similar challenges appear at the other end of the spectrum, where algorithms rely on data points that reflect “choice” and therefore ostensibly respect people's autonomy both by giving effect to their life choices and by allowing them to change course and extract themselves from untrusted groups. Here, the challenge is with the meaning of choice, as many actions that are putatively freely chosen may result from coercive social conditions or from lack of reasonable alternatives. This can apply to choices that span diverse life experiences, including familial status and parenthood, occupation, education, residence, cultural taste, dietary variety, and more. Many of these pieces of information, highly valuable from a predictive analysis perspective, could tie people to life conditions over which they may have only limited control. They may also be choices we would want people to make freely, without concern of sanction or penalty in the form of subsequent inclusion in their behavior prediction algorithms.²²⁷ Here, too, mutability turns out to be a matter of degree, and a normative evaluation of BRTs should therefore be sensitive to the contextual nature of such judgments.

²²⁶ Binns, *supra* note 114, at 7 (describing the “luck egalitarian aim of pursuing redistribution only where inequalities are due to pure luck, and leaving in place inequalities which are the result of personal choices and informed gambles,” and noting the normative complexities that go into making such distinctions).

²²⁷ *See id.*

2. Data Dynamism and Regulatory Experimentalism

A BRT that seeks to minimize infringement of rights on the one hand, and to maximize predictive accuracy on the other, must endeavor to remain robust over time, in the sense of maintaining a sensitivity to relevant changes in the empirical landscape as well as a capacity to adapt its design and operation to such developments. This entails two elements. First, we ought to incorporate data dynamism (or “concept drift”)²²⁸ into the algorithmic design to ensure that predictive analyses constantly update to reflect added data and the variability of people’s behaviors and choices. If the design of the BRT is committed to protecting the rights of regulatory subjects, then it must account for their evolving choices and tendencies and refrain from tying them to foregone behaviors. Indeed, a dynamic model would also have to consider gradually discounting past behavior information as it becomes more distant. While this could sometimes be required by accuracy measures as well—as old infractions become less likely to predict future ones—it is separately demanded by a privacy-based “right to be forgotten,” which has been articulated in the last decade with respect to lasting online footprints.²²⁹

Second, regulators should adopt an experimentalist approach to BRT design and deployment, given the possibility of unforeseen effects or evolving conditions.²³⁰ This means exercising an incrementalist approach that develops through an iterative process of pilots, audits, testing, and adjustment of the predictive tools, thus facilitating the identification and rectification of errors and injustices in the trust-based programs. The mechanism of “regulatory sandboxes” is a common method for fostering innovation in a regulated sector in a supervised environment;²³¹

²²⁸ Jie Lu et al., *Learning under Concept Drift: A Review*, 31 IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON KNOWLEDGE AND DATA ENGINEERING 2346 (2019).

²²⁹ See, e.g., Robert C. Post, *Data Privacy and Dignitary Privacy: Google Spain, the Right to be Forgotten, and the Construction of the Public Sphere*, 67 DUKE L.J. 981 (2018) (discussing how different conceptualizations of the scope of right to be forgotten can variably compact dignitary privacy and freedom of speech); Dominic McGoldrick, *Developments in the Right to be Forgotten*, 13 HUM. RTS. L. REV. 761 (2013); Maria Romana Allegri, *The Right to be Forgotten in the Digital Age*, in WHAT PEOPLE LEAVE BEHIND 237–51 (Francesca Comunello et al. eds., 2022) (discussing the legal development of the right, and its normative underpinnings, in the context of European law).

²³⁰ See Sofia Ranchordas, *Experimental Regulations for AI: Sandboxes for Morals and Mores*, 1 MORALS & MACHS. 86, 93, 98 (2021) (assessing the capacity of “experimental regulations and regulatory sandboxes” to ensure “that the impact of technology will be open to discussion, democratic supervision and control” and “contribute to the development of evidence-based lawmaking”); Mireille Hildebrandt, *Algorithmic Regulation and the Rule of Law*, 376 PHIL. TRANSACTIONS ROYAL SOC’Y A 1, 9 (2018) (calling the development of “artificial legal intelligence” to be conceived as a “a playground for well-designed experimentation, for developing new insights, argumentation patterns, for testing alternative approaches, for detecting missing information (facts, legal arguments), helping to improve the outcome of cases”).

²³¹ See, e.g., Hilary J. Allen, *Regulatory Sandboxes*, 87 GEO. WASH. L. REV. 579, 592 (2019) (describing the process as one in which “firms permitted to take advantage of a regulatory sandbox will be able to test their products with real customers in an environment that is not subject to the full panoply of rules that apply to regulated financial firms. Regulators will typically provide guidance as part of the regulatory sandbox model, with the intention of creating a collaborative relationship between regulator and regulated firm”).

regulators would do well to apply its logic to their own enforcement technologies as well.²³² In this way, through ongoing experimentation and refinement, BRTs can be fine-tuned to better balance competing interests, ensuring that the protection of rights remains paramount while still achieving regulatory goals effectively. Adaptive technologies that are open to review and remaking are therefore more likely to respect rights than rigid, predetermined programs.

V. PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

The normative framework developed in Part IV establishes constitutional boundaries for Behavioral Recognition Technologies: BRTs must privilege individual over group predictions, restrict cross-domain data use, ensure adequate accuracy, maintain transparency, and build in reversibility. These principles, however, require institutional translation. This Part demonstrates how agencies can operationalize trust-based regulation within these constraints, addressing three central implementation challenges: how to deploy BRT where constitutional risks are lowest while learning how systems perform (Section A), how to structure experimentation that generates evidence without sacrificing rights (Section B), and how to build capacity for responsible algorithmic governance (Section C).

A. *Corporate Contexts as Constitutional Proving Grounds*

The call that results from the normative analysis, to privilege individual predictions over group-based classifications, creates an immediate implementation puzzle: Individual behavioral assessment requires rich longitudinal data which regulatory agencies often lack, particularly when the regulated entities lack established compliance histories. The solution lies in recognizing that corporations and individuals present fundamentally different constitutional landscapes for BRT deployment.

Corporate regulatory contexts offer three decisive advantages. First, corporations generate extensive compliance data through mandatory reporting, permitting processes, and inspection histories, providing the empirical foundation for individualized predictions without invasive surveillance. The SEC’s ability to analyze billions of trading records through ARTEMIS reflects corporations’ thicker informational footprints. Second, corporations face attenuated privacy expectations,²³³ their regulatory interactions are instrumentally oriented rather than intimate,

²³² Katherine L. Milkman et al., *A 680,000-Person Megastudy of Nudges to Encourage Vaccination in Pharmacies*, 119 PROCS. NAT’L ACAD. SCI. U.S. OF AM. 1 (2022).

²³³ See *FCC v. AT&T Inc.*, 562 U.S. 397, 409-410 (2011) (holding that “[t]he protection in FOIA against disclosure of law enforcement information on the ground that it would constitute an unwarranted invasion of personal privacy does not extend to corporations;” Elizabeth Pollman, *A Corporate Right to Privacy*, 99 MINN. L. REV. 27, 32 (2014) (arguing that “most corporations in most circumstances should not have a constitutional right to privacy”).

making behavioral monitoring less constitutionally fraught. Third, and most critically, the dignitary harms that animate individual rights protections, such as stigma, humiliation, and constraints on self-authorship, apply with markedly different force to institutional actors.

These differences suggest a graduated implementation strategy: Deploy BRT first in corporate regulatory domains, establish working systems that demonstrably respect the framework's principles, then consider whether and how to extend behavioral trust assessment to individual regulatory subjects.

Existing regulatory programs already employ rudimentary trust differentiation in the corporate context: consider the EPA's Audit Policy, the IRS's Compliance Assurance Process, and the FDA's Voluntary Qualified Importer Program. These initiatives share a common structure: regulatory benefits (reduced inspections, expedited processing, penalty mitigation) flow to entities demonstrating sustained compliance. What they lack is systematic integration of behavioral prediction. Agencies should formalize multi-tiered compliance frameworks that explicitly link past behavioral indicators to current regulatory treatment, while accounting for the constitutional concerns invoked by differential trust regimes.

Thus, rather than binary trusted/untrusted classifications, which create the arbitrary line-drawing problems discussed above, agencies should establish graduated tiers reflecting meaningful behavioral differences. A corporate actor's tier placement should be determined not by ad hoc administrative discretion but by validated algorithms informed of their history of self-disclosure, response quality to regulatory inquiries, internal compliance investments, and violation patterns. The critical design choice requires calibrating tier benefits to compliance risk while avoiding the exploitation vulnerabilities that plague purely trust-based systems. For example, high-tier corporations might receive quarterly rather than monthly reporting obligations, expedited permit reviews, and eligibility for self-certification—meaningful administrative relief that incentivizes sustained compliance without eliminating oversight. Low-tier corporations would face enhanced monitoring, mandatory third-party audits, and priority targeting for unannounced inspections. This structure operationalizes the responsive regulation pyramid while grounding escalation decisions in behavioral evidence rather than regulator intuition.

A presumption against group-based predictions should underlie algorithmic design, so as to limit reliance on industry sector, geographic location, corporate size, or other demographic data points that might proxy for protected characteristics or perpetuate existing disparities. Tier assignments must reflect actual behavioral patterns, violation frequency and severity, disclosure practices, and remedial responsiveness.²³⁴ Similarly, the wariness of cross-domain behavioral

²³⁴ A parallel track, on which we do not elaborate in this article, would consider the use of Large Language Models in normative deliberation processes, including for the purpose of producing textual balancing frameworks of regulatory purposes and democratic values under sophisticated prompt engineering. At the current point such tools

inference becomes particularly salient in corporate contexts, where regulatory interactions span multiple agencies. Should OSHA workplace safety violations inform EPA environmental tier assignments? Empirical justification is necessary. Agencies must demonstrate that cross-domain inferences improve accuracy substantially and that the regulatory benefit outweighs coordination costs and gaming incentives. Absent strong evidence, behavioral predictions should remain domain-specific.

Corporate contexts could also call for greater flexibility in the application of the transparency principle, compared to individual regulatory subjects. While corporations deserve to understand tier-assignment criteria, when the regulatory subject is a sophisticated organization, full algorithmic disclosure risks gaming that undermines regulatory effectiveness. Agencies might thus be justified in disclosing behavioral factors (self-disclosure, response quality, violation patterns) without revealing precise weights or algorithmic architecture, striking the balance between accountability and strategic enforcement value.

Only after corporate BRT systems demonstrate sustained success—measurably improving compliance without creating discriminatory impacts, achieving accuracy rates that justify differential treatment, establishing working review mechanisms—should agencies consider BRT application to individuals. Even then, individual BRT demands stronger safeguards reflecting heightened constitutional stakes: mandatory human review for adverse determinations, explicit rehabilitation (trustworthiness reassessment) pathways, and strict scrutiny of BRT use for constitutionally protected activities. The corporate-first strategy serves epistemic and constitutional purposes simultaneously. It generates empirical evidence about algorithmic performance, identifies unanticipated failure modes, and builds institutional capacity before extending behavioral recognition to contexts where rights implications are most severe.

B. *Experimental Federalism and Evidentiary Foundations*

The constitutional demand that BRTs meet accuracy thresholds creates an evidentiary burden: Agencies must demonstrate that the behavioral predictions they use achieve sufficient validity to justify differential treatment. Yet determining “sufficient” accuracy cannot proceed purely theoretically as different regulatory contexts present different prediction challenges, baseline compliance rates, and enforcement constraints. Agencies require systematic evidence about how design choices affect performance. This points toward experimental regulatory

can at most inform the human process, not supplant it. See, e.g., Pratik Sachdeva & Tom van Nuenen, *Normative Evaluation of Large Language Models with Everyday Moral Dilemmas*, PROCEEDINGS OF THE 2025 ACM CONFERENCE 690 (2025) (finding that different models treat similar run-of-the-mill moral dilemmas in different ways with little consistency); Christoph Engel et al., *Human Realignment: An Empirical Study of LLMs as Legal Decision-Aids in Moral Dilemmas*, DISCUSSION PAPERS OF THE MAX PLANCK INST. FOR RSCH. ON COLLECTIVE GOODS 1 (2025) (finding that difference models seem partial to different moral philosophies in dealing with trolley-problem moral challenges).

federalism: deploying BRT through controlled variation that tests critical design parameters while limiting exposure to unvalidated systems. Rather than wholesale algorithmic implementation, agencies should structure regulatory pilot programs that compare alternative approaches, measure outcomes rigorously, and adjust designs based on evidence.

Several implementation choices require empirical guidance: (1) *Accuracy thresholds*: As we explained above, statistical significance alone cannot justify differential treatment; effect sizes must be meaningful. But what predictive accuracy justifies reduced inspections or an expedited permitting process? If an algorithm achieves 75% accuracy predicting violations, does that warrant tier-based treatment, or must accuracy exceed 85% or 90%? These questions cannot be resolved abstractly; they depend on violation consequences, baseline rates, and administrative costs. (2) *Transparency mechanisms*: The demand for algorithmic explainability does not specify the degree of transparency that suffices for legitimacy while limiting gaming. Should agencies disclose general factors, specific weights, complete model architecture, or individualized feedback? Each choice presents different tradeoffs between accountability and strategic behavior. (3) *Rehabilitation pathways*: Reversibility demands that low-trust designations remain non-permanent, but optimal rehabilitation mechanisms remain unclear. For example, should trust restoration (or upgrade) occur automatically after predetermined violation-free periods? Through graduated performance improvement? Or via affirmative demonstration of reformed practices?

To address these uncertainties, agencies can employ randomized field experiments that test design variations. Superior to elaborate research protocols, the approach reflects regulatory pragmatism: When agencies lack evidence to choose between plausible approaches, assign different designs to comparable regulated populations and measure outcomes.

For accuracy thresholds, an agency might compare traditional enforcement against algorithmic targeting at varying stringency levels within a single program. OSHA's inspection scheduling provides a natural experiment opportunity: Randomly assign facilities to traditional scheduling versus algorithmic prioritization at different accuracy cutoffs, then track violation detection rates, injury outcomes, and administrative costs. Evidence about performance differences informs decisions about minimum accuracy justifying BRT deployment.

For transparency, agencies might provide different corporations with varying levels of algorithmic disclosure, ranging from no information about tier-assignment mechanics to complete model transparency. They can then measure perceived legitimacy, gaming behavior, and compliance outcomes. If full transparency enables manipulation without improving legitimacy, that evidence supports less disclosure; if opacity undermines cooperation, greater transparency becomes justified.

These regulatory experiments serve constitutional as well as administrative purposes. Courts evaluating BRT systems under due process or equal protection scrutiny will demand evidence that algorithmic classifications serve legitimate state interests and avoid arbitrary distinctions. Experimental evidence demonstrating that specific designs improve outcomes measurably while respecting rights provides the empirical foundation for constitutional justification.

C. Institutional Capacity for Algorithmic Governance

The framework's requirements—individualized predictions, cross-domain restrictions, accuracy validation, transparency mechanisms, and reversibility pathways—demand institutional capabilities most regulatory agencies currently lack. Responsible BRT implementation requires not merely deploying existing tools but building governance infrastructure adequate to the technology's complexity and constitutional stakes. Notably, Algorithmic regulation requires integrating technical, legal, and domain expertise in ways traditional agency structures do not facilitate. Statistical validation demands data science capabilities; constitutional compliance requires sustained legal analysis; effective implementation needs regulatory subject-matter knowledge. Few agencies possess all three in coordinated form.

Agencies should therefore endeavor to establish specialized algorithmic governance divisions that would combine these competences. These units would design BRT systems, validate predictive models, monitor for disparate impacts, conduct algorithmic audits, and maintain documentation supporting legal challenges. The SEC's Crypto Assets and Cyber Unit provides a structural model: a specialized division with dedicated expertise addressing a domain requiring technical sophistication and regulatory judgment.

Critically, these divisions must include not only technical staff but also civil rights and constitutional specialists. The tendency to treat algorithmic design as purely technical, optimizing accuracy without attending to rights implications, produces systems that perform well statistically but may disregard violating constitutional norms. Building rights protection into algorithmic architecture requires legal expertise at the design stage, not merely post hoc review.

At the same time, agencies ought to establish regular algorithmic impact assessments examining whether systems avoid discriminatory outcomes, achieve claimed accuracy rates, and respect cross-domain limitations. These audits should be public, be conducted by parties independent of system designers, and provide detailed analysis sufficient for meaningful external review. In this way, BRT transparency is extended beyond explaining individual determinations and aims at systemic accountability—allowing legislatures, courts, and the public to verify that BRT systems operate as claimed and respect constitutional boundaries.

The IRS's recent announcement of algorithmic tax enforcement illustrates the accountability gap: While the agency disclosed that AI would target high-income tax filers, it provided minimal information about how algorithms identify compliance risk, what data they use, or how accuracy is validated. This opacity prevents meaningful democratic oversight. Agencies employing BRT should publish annual algorithmic accountability reports detailing system architecture, performance metrics, disparate impact analysis, and changes implemented based on evidence.

Implementing the normative framework developed in this Article thus demands institutional changes beyond deploying algorithmic tools: specialized expertise, experimental methods, accountability mechanisms, and doctrinal evolution. The corporate-first strategy minimizes constitutional risk while building capacity; experimental federalism generates evidence supporting design choices; institutional reforms create governance infrastructure adequate to BRT's complexity. Together, these practical implications demonstrate that responsible algorithmic regulation is achievable, but only through sustained attention to the democratic and constitutional foundations that legitimize governmental power.

CONCLUSION

This Article addresses what may be the defining constitutional challenge of algorithmic governance: whether predictive technologies can enable a more responsive regulatory state without sacrificing the foundational commitments of dignity, equality, and democratic accountability that legitimize governmental authority in a free society. By bringing behavioral recognition technology into systematic legal focus for the first time, this Article fills a critical void in both AI governance scholarship and administrative and constitutional law theory. While facial recognition has dominated debates about algorithmic state power, behavioral prediction systems have proliferated across regulatory domains with virtually no theoretical framework to guide their design or constrain their deployment. This Article has provided that framework. Our normative blueprint establishes concrete principles for evaluating when and how government may permissibly use past conduct to predict future compliance, calibrating the scope of cross-domain data integration to constitutional requirements and embedding reversibility and accountability mechanisms into algorithmic architecture. These principles represent more than aspirational guidelines. They constitute enforceable standards grounded in established constitutional doctrine yet adapted to the distinctive challenges of machine learning systems that continuously reshape the relationship between citizen and state.

The stakes could not be higher. Federal agencies face unprecedented resource constraints even as regulatory complexity intensifies, creating powerful incentives to adopt algorithmic trust

assessment without adequate normative deliberation. Yet the path forward need not choose between efficiency and rights, between innovation and constitutional constraint. Properly designed behavioral recognition systems can simultaneously enhance regulatory effectiveness, reduce compliance burdens on trustworthy actors, and vindicate rather than undermine constitutional values by enabling genuinely individualized treatment that escapes the crude demographic proxies of traditional enforcement. Realizing this potential requires precisely what this Article provides: a rigorous analytical framework that integrates insights from behavioral science, administrative law, and constitutional theory to guide the design of trust-based regulatory technologies. As agencies accelerate their adoption of algorithmic tools, courts confront novel constitutional questions, and legislatures consider comprehensive AI governance frameworks, this Article's principles offer essential guidance for ensuring that behavioral prediction serves democratic governance rather than displacing it. The regulatory state's legitimacy in an age of automation depends on getting these foundational questions right.